

Analysis of a summary statistics generated from the UK Biobank database: new potential risk loci for ME/CFS and not otherwise specified chronic asthenia

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Abstract

I present here an analysis of the summary statistics elaborated by Neale's Lab from the raw data released by the UK Biobank, a large-scale biomedical database that includes genetic data on 500,000 UK citizens. I filtered out variants with a minor allele frequency below 0.05, I included only variants that reached a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ (even though only $p < 5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ was considered for definitive associations), I filtered out variants with a p value for the Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium below 10^{-6} .

Females with self-reported Chronic Fatigue Syndrome are associated with a region of chromosome 13 with high linkage disequilibrium, that goes from position 41353297 to 41404706 (on h19) that completely includes gene SLC25A15. After applying statistical methods of fine-mapping (approximation of the joint model and posterior inclusion probability, PIP), I found rs11147812 (13:41404706:T:C) as the possible causal variant within this region. This same variant is associated with the whole sample of patients (males + females) at $5 \cdot 10^{-8} < p < 5 \cdot 10^{-7}$. The relaxed cut-off for statistical significance of $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ has been recently proposed as a way to increase the rate of true positives without a substantial increase in false positive associations, in studies with a sample of 130,000. This variant is included in pseudogene TPTE2P5, which is known to be translated into mRNA and which is associated, in other GWAS studies, with diastolic blood pressure.

Males with chronic asthenia not otherwise specified (ICD10: R53) showed an association with a region in high LD of chromosome 18 (18:55452281 to 18:55460845). The only variant from this region with $p < 5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ is rs62092652 (18:55454761:G:A) and it is confirmed as the causal variant in this region by PIP calculation. The alternative allele at this position is associated with a reduced expression of gene ATP8B1 in the brain. Since the alternative allele is more frequent in patients than in controls (frequency of 0.3501 and 0.2422, respectively), we may expect to find a reduced expression of ATP8B1 in the brain of patients. ATP8B1 encodes a member of the P-type cation transport ATPase family, which transport phosphatidylserine and phosphatidylethanolamine from one side of a bilayer to another. These two molecules are both phospholipids found in biological membranes. A decreased level of phospholipids has been reported in ME/CFS by many plasma metabolomic studies.

I also performed a similar analysis on variants with a minor allele frequency below 0.05 and above 0.01 (by using a more stringent cut-off $p < 10^{-8}$) and I found an association between ME/CFS (both sexes) and a possible regulatory region of EBF3, a gene that encodes a member of the early B-cell factor (EBF) family of DNA binding transcription factors. EBF proteins are involved in B-cell differentiation, bone development and neurogenesis, and may also function as tumor suppressors. According to this analysis, females with R53 are different from controls with respect to variant rs182581502 (7:56492485:G:T on h19), with the alternative allele more frequent in patients than in controls. This is an intronic variant of pseudogene RP13-492C18.2 (gene_id: ENSG00000237268.2). This variant is associated with changes in gene expression of gene CHCHD2 in several tissues (see [this page](#)). The alternative allele (the one more frequent in female R53 patients) is associated with an increase in the expression of CHCHD2 in the hippocampus and basal ganglia, for instance. No associations were found for males only. All the results are collected in Table 22.

Genetic data from the UK Biobank were also used to test previously proposed associations between ME/CFS and variants on TNF α : none of the proposed associations was confirmed.

No overlap of the genetic signal from self-reported CFS and R53 was found with the psychiatric traits: bipolar II and depression.

This document also includes an introduction to some of the methods currently employed in the study of GWAS summary statistics.

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“The only thing that is arbitrary about the various orders of a set of terms is our attention, for the terms themselves have always all the orders of which they are capable.”

Bertrand Russell, *Introduction to Mathematical Philosophy*

1 Introduction

The UK Biobank is a large-scale biomedical database that includes genetic data on 500,000 UK citizens (Sudlow, C et al. 2015). Myalgic Encephalomyelitis/Chronic Fatigue Syndrome (ME/CFS) is among the phenotypes reported by participants. The total number of ME/CFS patients included is 1208 females and 451 males, with control groups of more than 150 k individuals each. For each individual, 805,426 variants (both SNPs and short InDels) were genotyped. From them, up to 30 million variants can be imputed using haplotype maps. This is the biggest GWAS study on ME/CFS patients ever made, so far. Many research groups have analyzed this huge quantity of data and the conclusion, according to (Dibble J. et al. 2020), is that the only variants to be significantly different between patients and controls are included in gene SLC25A15, which encodes mitochondrial ornithine transporter I, particularly variant rs7337312 (position13:41353297:G:A on reference genome GRCh37, forward strand). But this difference is statistically significant only when we consider female patients vs female controls. For a detailed discussion of this result, the best reference is the already mentioned (Dibble J. et al. 2020).

In this document, I present some analysis of the summary statistics elaborated by Neale's Lab from the raw data released by the UK Biobank (see par. 4.1). I have filtered out variants with a minor allele frequency below 0.05, I have included only variants that reached a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ (see par 4.6 for a discussion on how this number is calculated), I have filtered out variants with a p value for the Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium below 10^{-6} (see par. 4.2.1, 4.6.6 for a detailed discussion of these steps). I have considered only the phenotypes in Table 30 (except for I95, Hypotension). I have associated each one of the variants selected by this process to the gene(s) they belong to (if any) by using the software presented in 4.2.3 and I have also deduced the allele frequencies in patients and controls, from the data included in the summary statistics (method in par. 4.2.2). I have assigned a score of pathogenicity (C score) to the selected variants, according to what described in par. 0. A mathematical approach to fine-mapping the results has been applied, when helpful (par. 4.8). In particular, I introduce here software I have written for the search of the true causal variants in a region with high linkage disequilibrium when only the univariate regression analysis is available (as it is the case with summary statistics). My software is described in par. 4.8 and it is applied to the data here discussed. While it can reliably calculate the true effect sizes, it can't calculate reliably their standard errors, at present. For this reason, I have used, along with my software, the R package SusieR for a definitive answer on causal variants (see par. 4.8.7). I also performed a similar analysis on variants with a minor allele frequency below 0.05 and above 0.01 (by using a more stringent cut-off $p < 10^{-8}$). All the results are collected in Table 22.

2 Results

2.1 Phenotype 20002_1482 (chronic fatigue syndrome)

The search for associations between phenotype 20002_1482 (Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome) and genotyped/imputed variants, has generated the results collected in Table 11, Table 12, and Table 13 for both sexes, females only, males only, respectively. Only variants in green cells must be considered strong associations, while all the others must be considered only suggestive associations (see par. 4.6.4).

2.1.1 Both sexes

None of the variants available reaches a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ when we consider males and females lumped together (Table 11). If we consider the relaxed p value of $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$, suggested for GWAS studies with more than 130k participants (in our case $n \sim 361k$), we find five variants. None

of them has a scaled C-score above 10 (they are all below 5) and none has been associated with a trait, according to the GWAS catalog for trait associations. If we look at the gene level and by interrogating the GWAS catalog, we find that both ADAMTS20 and CNBD1 contain variants that have been associated with cortical surface area measurement and cortical thickness, and those are their best associations, i.e. those with the lowest p values (see Table 2). The best associations for variants included in TPTE2P5 are for diastolic blood pressure and blood volume occupied by platelets. Note that while TPTE2P5 is a pseudogene, it is expressed in several tissues, like the thyroid, duodenum, and liver (R), and this might explain the presence of traits associated with it, but consider that those associations might also arise from variants that belong to an overlapping protein-coding gene. Therefore, if the association of the first three variants of Table 11 was confirmed by future studies, a possible role for rs559328512, 8:88078555_TGTTACATA_T in the genesis of symptoms of cognitive dysfunction could be speculated, while rs11147812 might play a role in orthostatic hypotension/tachycardia. But it must be noted that the alternative allele of rs11147812 has been associated with an increase in the gene expression of SLC25A15 in various tissue, mainly adipose tissue (Table 1). Since the alternative allele is less frequent in patients than in controls (0.4414 and 0.4864, respectively) we expect a reduced expression of SLC25A15 in adipose tissue and other tissues.

Gene	P-value (-log10)	Effect size	Tissue
ENSG00000102743	20.45516	0.207934	fat
ENSG00000102743	15.27035	0.206953	adipose_naive
ENSG00000102743	11.03523	0.203519	fibroblast
ENSG00000102743	10.62467	0.175998	LCL
ENSG00000102743	8.77219	0.09993	iPSC

Table 1. The influence of variant rs11147812 on tissue-specific gene expression, from Ensemble. The effect size is positive, which means that the alternative allele increases gene expression of SLC25A15 in all the tissues indicated.

2.1.2 Females only

When we consider females only, we find 34 variants with a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$, and 11 of them have a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$. None of them has a scaled C-score above 10 (they are all below 5) and none has been associated with a trait, according to the GWAS catalog for trait associations. We find again the variant on TPTE2P5 (and the other two close to it) selected by the relaxed cut-off ($5 \cdot 10^{-7}$) in the study including both sexes but we also find 5 variants on SLC25A15 and close by regions. If we look at the correlation coefficient ρ for the 11 variants with the lowest p value (Table 3), we discover that they are all in high linkage disequilibrium. This means that we can't say, without further analysis, whether the causal variants belong to TPTE2P5 or SLC25A15. By applying the mathematical methods of fine-mapping described in par. 4.8, and in particular in par. 4.8.4, 4.8.5, 4.8.7.1, and 4.8.7.2, we conclude that the true causal variant in this region of high LD is rs11147812, the same variant found for the comparison including both sexes (see the previous paragraph). Also in the case of female patients, we see a reduced frequency of the alternative allele of variant rs11147812, with respect to controls (0.4246 and 0.4864, respectively) and we conclude that we expect a reduced expression of gene SLC25A15 in the tissues collected in Table 1.

2.1.3 Males only

None of the variants available reaches a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ when we consider males only (Table 13Table 11). If we consider the relaxed p value of $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ we find two variants. The intergenic variant rs117712647 has no known effect, to my knowledge. The alternative allele of rs45498702 is associated with a reduced expression of gene CAV2 (click on the gene for details) in the pancreas,

along with other effects (click on the variant in Table 13 to explore the available data). Neither of the two has a scaled C-score above 10.

2.2 Phenotype R53 (malaise and fatigue)

The search for associations between phenotype R53 (malaise and fatigue) and genotyped/imputed variants, has generated the results collected in Table 14, Table 15, and Table 16 for both sexes, females only, and males only, respectively. Only variants in green cells must be considered strong associations, while all the others must be considered only suggestive associations (see par. 4.6.4).

Gene	Traits associate with variants included in this gene	p value	Reference
ADAMTS20	Cortical surface area measurement	$1 \cdot 10^{-17}$	Shadrin AA et al. 2021
	Cortical thickness	$2 \cdot 10^{-12}$	
	Height	$3 \cdot 10^{-8}$	Kichaev G et al. 2019
	Intraocular pression	$3 \cdot 10^{-8}$	Choquet H et al. 2017
TPTE2P5	Diastolic blood pressure	$9 \cdot 10^{-11}$	Evangelou E et al. 2018
	Blood volume occupied by platelets	$7 \cdot 10^{-10}$	Astle WG et al. 2016
	Basophil count	$1 \cdot 10^{-8}$	Masahiro K et al. 2018
CNBD1	Cortical surface area measurement	$1 \cdot 10^{-16}$	Shadrin AA et al. 2021
	Cortical thickness	$2 \cdot 10^{-11}$	
	Smoking initiation	$1 \cdot 10^{-10}$	Mengzhen L et al. 2019
	Educational attainment	$4 \cdot 10^{-9}$	James JL et al. 2018
	Adult body size	$2 \cdot 10^{-8}$	Richardson TG et al. 2020
	Weight	$4 \cdot 10^{-8}$	Saori S et al. 2021

Table 2. The most significant associations ($p < 5 \cdot 10^{-8}$) for variants included in ADAMTS20, TPTE2P5, and CNBD1. Click on the gene's name to open the corresponding page on the GWAS catalog.

	rs7337312										
rs7337312	1.0000	0.8877	0.8877	0.9157	0.8823	0.8958	0.8956	0.8961	0.8932	0.8938	0.7747
rs368309529	0.8877	1.0000	0.9482	0.8918	0.8591	0.8731	0.8729	0.8734	0.8707	0.8713	0.7925
rs564453195	0.8877	0.9482	1.0000	0.8918	0.8591	0.8731	0.8729	0.8734	0.8707	0.8713	0.7925
rs7997189	0.9157	0.8918	0.8918	1.0000	0.8868	0.9002	0.9001	0.9006	0.8977	0.8983	0.7790
rs1536807	0.8823	0.8591	0.8591	0.8868	1.0000	0.9326	0.9324	0.9329	0.9301	0.9307	0.8120
rs6563846	0.8958	0.8731	0.8731	0.9002	0.9326	1.0000	0.9458	0.9463	0.9434	0.9440	0.8257
rs2282023	0.8956	0.8729	0.8729	0.9001	0.9324	0.9458	1.0000	0.9461	0.9432	0.9438	0.8256
rs2282026	0.8961	0.8734	0.8734	0.9006	0.9329	0.9463	0.9461	1.0000	0.9437	0.9443	0.8260
rs2017696	0.8932	0.8707	0.8707	0.8977	0.9301	0.9434	0.9432	0.9437	1.0000	0.9414	0.8233
rs7330720	0.8938	0.8713	0.8713	0.8983	0.9307	0.9440	0.9438	0.9443	0.9414	1.0000	0.8239
rs11147812	0.7747	0.7925	0.7925	0.7790	0.8120	0.8257	0.8256	0.8260	0.8233	0.8239	1.0000

Table 3. Linkage disequilibrium measured as $\rho_{i,j}$ between each possible couple of the first variants in Table 12. This calculation is based on the allele frequencies of the control group in Table 38, while the frequencies of each possible binary haplotype were calculated from data collected in Table 39.

	rs2571227										
rs2571227	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.9736	0.9903	0.9842	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
rs7240802	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.9819	0.9987	0.9924	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
rs2571234	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.9809	0.9978	0.9915	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
rs2850243	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.9920	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
rs2850244	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.9931	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
rs62092652	0.9736	0.9819	0.9809	0.9920	0.9931	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.9956	0.9945	0.9967
rs2663855	0.9903	0.9987	0.9978	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
rs2571236	0.9842	0.9924	0.9915	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
rs2663854	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.9956	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
rs2663853	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.9945	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
rs2663851	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.9967	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000

Table 4. Linkage disequilibrium measured as $\rho_{i,j}$ between each possible couple of the first variants in Table 16. This calculation is based on the allele frequencies of the control group in Table 16, while the frequencies of each possible binary haplotype were calculated from data collected in Table 5.

2.2.1 Males only

One of the variants available reaches a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ when we consider males only (Table 16 Table 11) and if we consider the relaxed p value of $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ we find a region of several variants of chromosome 18 in high linkage disequilibrium with it (see Table 4). When we apply the software SusieR to this region, we find that the variant with the highest probability of being the causal one is rs62092652 (see 4.8.7.3 for details), which is also the only one with a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$. The alternative allele at this position is associated with a reduced expression of gene ATP8B1 in the brain (click on the variant in Table 16 for the details). Since the alternative allele is more frequent in patients than in controls (frequency of 0.3501 and 0.2422, respectively), we may expect to find a reduced expression of ATP8B1 in the brain of patients.

Haplotype	Count	Frequency
T_A_A_A_A_G_T_G_C_A_C	116	0.6374
C_G_C_G_G_A_C_A_T_G_T	49	0.2692
C_G_C_G_G_G_T_G_T_G_T	7	0.0385
C_G_C_A_A_G_T_G_C_A_C	4	0.022
C_A_A_A_A_G_T_G_C_A_C	1	0.0055
C_A_A_A_A_G_T_G_T_G_T	1	0.0055
C_G_C_G_G_G_C_G_T_G_T	1	0.0055
T_A_A_A_A_G_T_G_T_A_C	1	0.0055
T_A_A_A_A_G_T_G_T_G_T	1	0.0055
T_A_A_G_G_G_T_G_T_G_T	1	0.0055

Table 5. Frequencies of all the haplotypes present in the GBR population, when we consider the variants collected in Table 16.

2.3 Phenotype 20002_1542 (fibromyalgia)

The search for associations between phenotype 20002_1542 (Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: fibromyalgia) and genotyped/imputed variants, has generated the results collected in Table

17 for females only. This phenotype was not available for males only. In the group of females only, none of the variants reached a statistically significant association. Only variants in green cells must be considered strong associations, while all the others must be considered only suggestive associations (see par. 4.6.4).

2.4 Phenotype 20126_2 (bipolar II disorder)

For this phenotype, I could not use the relaxed cut-off for significance (the groups were too small), so I only applied the cut-off $p < 5 \cdot 10^{-8}$. We have associations with variants only for females only (Table 18) and for males only (Table 19). Only variants in green cells must be considered strong associations, while all the others must be considered only suggestive associations (see par. 4.6.4).

2.5 Phenotype F5_DEPRESSIO (depression)

The search for associations between phenotype F5_DEPRESSIO and genotyped/imputed variants, has generated the results collected in Table 20, and Table 21 for females only and males only, respectively. No significant association was found for the group including both sexes. Only variants in green cells must be considered strong associations, while all the others must be considered only suggestive associations (see par. 4.6.4).

2.6 Further analyses and summary table

I also performed a similar analysis on variants with a minor allele frequency below 0.05 and above 0.01. I used a more stringent cut-off for statistical significance of $1 \cdot 10^{-8}$ (72). The results of these two analysis are collected in Table 22. Note that the variants of this table are the origin of the association signal, but this signal must be regarded as coming from a region centered in the variant rather than from the variants itself, because in a GWAS only a few millions variants of the whole genome have a genotype. We can define a region as the source of the association signal by considering, among the genotyped/imputed variants, the variant that precedes and the variant that follows each call of Table 23.

3 Discussion

When we consider self-reported chronic fatigue, only the female group is associated with variants with a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ (Table 12). The signal comes from a region of chromosome 13 that goes from position 41353297 to 41404706 (on h19) that completely includes gene SLC25A15 (which spans from position 41363548 to 41384247). If we consider a relaxed p value of $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$, we find further variants included in this same region. These variants are in high linkage disequilibrium (LD), as can be seen in Table 3 and this means that the causal variant (the one that drives the association with the phenotype) might be only one of them, while the associations with the other variants are only a consequence of high LD (see par. 4.7). In cases like this (which are a common outcome of marginal associations in GWAS), a fine-mapping approach is warranted (see par. 4.8). By using my software for approximating the joint model from the marginal one (par. 4.8.4) we find rs11147812 (13:41404706:T:C) as the possible causal variant within this region. By fine-mapping with the method of posterior inclusion probability (PIP) by using the R library SusieR (see par. 4.8.7) we confirm rs11147812 as the possible causal variant, given this dataset. It can be seen that this variant survives at a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ when we consider males and females lumped together (Table 11). The meaning and the origin of the two cut-offs for significance that are used here ($5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ and $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$) are discussed in par. 4.6.4. Variant rs11147812 falls into TPTE2P5 which, despite being a pseudogene, is expressed in several tissues, like the thyroid, duodenum, and liver (R). In the GWAS

catalog, this gene is associated with changes in diastolic blood pressure and blood volume occupied by platelets (Table 2). The alternative allele of rs11147812 has been associated with an increase in the gene expression of SLC25A15 in various tissue, mainly adipose tissue (Table 1). Since the alternative allele is less frequent in patients than in controls (0.4414 and 0.4864 respectively, when we consider both sexes together and 0.4246 and 0.4864 respectively, when we consider females only) we expect a reduced expression of SLC25A15 in adipose tissue and in other tissues.

Gene SLC25A15 encodes mitochondrial ornithine transporter I which is involved in the transport of ornithine inside mitochondria, where it is metabolized into citrulline, and in doing so it consumes ammonium (NH_4^+), the conjugate acid of ammonia (NH_3) (see Figure 1 and Table 6). What might be the consequence (if any) of a reduction in the expression of this transporter in adipose tissue is not clear.

Figure 1. Urea cycle in a hepatocyte. From (Salway J. G. 2017), with changes. Chart by Paolo Maccallini.

When we consider the phenotype **ICD10: R53** (which includes chronic asthenia not otherwise specified, and as such might include some cases of misdiagnosed ME/CFS), we find a signal in the male group, from chromosome 18 (Table 16). Only the variant at position 18:55454761 has a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ and when we use the relaxed p value of $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ we find several other variants in the same region (from position 18:55452281 to 18:55460845) in high LD (Table 4). When we apply the software SusieR to this region, we find that the variant with the highest probability of being the causal

one is rs62092652 (see 4.8.7.3 for details), which is also the only one with a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$. The alternative allele at this position is associated with a reduced expression of gene ATP8B1 in the brain (click on the variant in Table 16 for the details). Since the alternative allele is more frequent in patients than in controls (frequency of 0.3501 and 0.2422, respectively), we may expect to find a reduced expression of ATP8B1 in the brain of patients. ATP8B1 encodes a member of the P-type cation transport ATPase family, which transports phosphatidylserine and phosphatidylethanolamine from one side of a bilayer to another (R). These two molecules are both phospholipids found in biological membranes. As a recent metabolomic study on ME/CFS pointed out: “The common threads in the results from all these studies are decreased levels of phospholipids” (Che X. et al. 2022), which refers to the metabolomic studies published in the last 6 years on ME/CFS. For instance, in one of these studies, phospholipid abnormalities constituted 16% of the metabolic disturbances in males and 26% in females (Naviaux et al. 2016).

Transporter (gene)	Metabolite	Enzymes (gene)	
	<u>ammonium</u>	carbamoyl phosphate synthetase I (<u>CPS1</u>)	ornithine transcarbamoylase (<u>OTC</u>)
	<u>carbamoyl phosphate</u>		
ornithine translocase (<u>SLC25A15</u>)	<u>ornithine</u>	argininosuccinate synthase I (<u>ASS1</u>)	argininosuccinate lyase (<u>ASL</u>)
	<u>citrulline</u>		
	<u>aspartate</u>	arginase 1 (<u>ARG1</u>)	
	<u>argininosuccinate</u>		
	<u>fumarate</u>		
	<u>arginine</u>		
ornithine translocase (<u>SLC25A15</u>)	<u>ornithine</u>		
	<u>urea</u>		

Table 6. Enzymes and metabolites that are involved in the Urea Cycle.

Among the other phenotypes included in the analysis (Fibromyalgia, Bipolar II, Depression) only Bipolar II showed a signal at a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$, which might be worth investigating, since Bipolar II is strongly characterized by fatigue. But it must be noticed that the signals from the two psychiatric phenotypes considered do not overlap with the signals from CFS and Chronic Fatigue (R53).

We can also use the data from the UK Biobank to verify the validity of the huge amount of associations proposed between fatigue in general, ME/CFS in particular, and genetic variants (see for instance the encyclopedic review Whang T. et al. 2017). As an example, I will focus on the variants of TNF alpha gene collected in Table 7. In 2006, an Italian group found that the minor allele of variant rs1799724 (TNF-857) was significantly more frequent in 54 ME/CFS patients than in 224 controls (Carlo-Stella N. et al. 2006). In 2020, a group from Germany reported a statistically significant difference for the same variant, but only when ME/CFS patients without infectious triggered onset were considered (Steiner S. et al. 2020). Two other variants of gene TNF alpha were associated with morning fatigue among oncology outpatients with breast, prostate, lung, or brain cancer (Dhruva A. et al. 2015). Are these variants different between 1659 ME/CFS patients and the about 300 k controls in the UK Biobank database? The full analysis, with the methods and the scripts I used, can be found in (Maccallini P. 2021). The results are collected in Table 8, Table 9, Table 10, Figure 2, and Figure 3. The conclusion is that none of the proposed associations is confirmed.

Variant	Position (h19)	Disease	p value	Reference
rs1799724	ch6:31,542,482	ME/CFS ME/CFS w/o ITO	0.0028 0.0430	Carlo-Stella N. et al. 2006 Steiner S. et al. 2020
rs1800629 rs3093662	ch6:31,543,031 ch6:31,544,189	Morning fatigue in oncology outpatients with breast, prostate, lung, or brain cancer	0.0250 0.0040	Dhruva A. et al. 2015

Table 7. Variants on gene TNF associated with ME/CFS, with ME/CFS without Infectious Triggered Onset (ITO), and with morning fatigue in oncology outpatients with breast, prostate, lung, or brain cancer. From ([Maccallini P. 2021](#)).

Rsid	min	ref	alt	min_AF	p value	alt AF cases	alt AF Controls
1799724	T	C	T	0.072	0.150	0.077	0.072
1800629	A	G	A	0.197	0.706	0.195	0.197
3093662	G	A	G	0.076	0.590	0.073	0.076

Table 8. Frequencies of the same variants in Table 7 from Neale's Lab Metadata. This is the comparison between 1656 ME/CFS patients (females + males) and 359482 controls (females + males) min = minor allele; ref = reference allele; alt = alternate allele; min AF = minor allele frequency. From ([Maccallini P. 2021](#))

Rsid	min	ref	alt	min_AF	p value	alt AF cases	alt AF Controls
1799724	T	C	T	0.072	0.167	0.078	0.071
1800629	A	G	A	0.197	0.857	0.198	0.196
3093662	G	A	G	0.076	0.603	0.073	0.076

Table 9. As in Table 8, but in this case the comparison is between 1208 female ME/CFS patients and 192945 female controls. Min = minor allele; ref = reference allele; alt = alternate allele; min AF = minor allele frequency. From ([Maccallini P. 2021](#)).

Rsid	min	ref	alt	min_AF	p value	alt AF cases	alt AF Controls
1799724	T	C	T	0.072	0.609	0.075	0.072
1800629	A	G	A	0.197	0.314	0.186	0.199
3093662	G	A	G	0.076	0.856	0.074	0.075

Table 10. As in Table 8 and Table 9, but in this case the comparison is between 451 male ME/CFS patients and 166537 male controls. Min = minor allele; ref = reference allele; alt = alternate allele; min AF = minor allele frequency. From ([Maccallini P. 2021](#)).

Figure 2. Manhattan plot for ch6:31,539,768 – ch6:31,546,495, in the case of female + male CFS patients vs controls. The red dot is rs1799724, the blue dot is rs1800629, and the yellow dot is rs3093662. None of these three variants reaches a p value below 10^{-1} . From ([Maccallini P. 2021](#)).

Figure 3. Manhattan plot for ch6:31,539,768 – ch6:31,546,495, in the case of female CFS patients vs female controls (left) and male CFS patients vs male controls (right). The red dot is rs1799724, the blue dot is rs1800629, and the yellow dot is rs3093662. None of these three variants reaches a p value below 10^{-1} . From (Maccallini P. 2021).

Variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
12:43803404:C:CAAAAAAAAA	rs559328512	intron variant	C	4.81E-01	2.57E-07	0.4753	0.5192	ENSG00000173157.12	protein coding	ADAMTS20	
13:41404706:T:C	rs11147812	intron variant	C	4.86E-01	3.29E-07	0.4414	0.4864	ENSG00000168852.8	pseudo gene	TPTE2P5	
8:88078555:TGTTACATA:T	8:88078555_TGTTACATA_T	intron variant	T	5.41E-02	3.86E-07	0.0349	0.0542	ENSG00000176571.7	protein coding	CNBD1	
13:41358365:CT:C	rs368309529	intergenic variant	C	4.74E-01	4.77E-07	0.4303	0.4744				
13:41358369:T:C	rs564453195	intergenic variant	C	4.74E-01	4.77E-07	0.4303	0.4744				

Table 11. Phenotype 20002_1482 (chronic fatigue syndrome), both sexes. From lowest p value to highest. n cases = 1659, n controls = 359482. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page. Click on the rsid to open the relative Ensembl page.

variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
13:41404706:T:C	rs11147812	intron variant	C	4.86E-01	1.63E-09	0.4246	0.4864	ENSG00000168852.8	pseudo gene	TPTE2P5	
13:41358365:CT:C	rs368309529	intergenic variant	C	4.74E-01	2.92E-09	0.4139	0.4745				
13:41358369:T:C	rs564453195	intergenic variant	C	4.74E-01	2.92E-09	0.4139	0.4745				
13:41387065:T:A	rs2017696	downstream gene variant	T	4.86E-01	3.41E-09	0.4537	0.5148				5.023
13:41390881:G:A	rs7330720	intergenic variant	G	4.86E-01	4.02E-09	0.4537	0.5145				
13:41374328:C:G	rs2282023	intron variant	C	4.87E-01	7.49E-09	0.4538	0.5136	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41370996:A:G	rs6563846	intron variant	A	4.87E-01	7.74E-09	0.4538	0.5135	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41381077:G:A	rs2282026	intron variant	G	4.87E-01	7.75E-09	0.4536	0.5133	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41369790:A:G	rs1536807	intron variant	A	4.91E-01	9.55E-09	0.4499	0.5092	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	5.945
13:41353297:G:A	rs7337312	regulatory region variant	G	4.95E-01	2.56E-08	0.4478	0.5057				
13:41363595:T:C	rs7997189	non coding transcript exon variant	T	4.97E-01	3.50E-08	0.4464	0.5035	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	6.582

13:41378679:AT:A	13:41378679_AT_A	intron variant	AT	4.83E-01	5.42E-08	0.4622	0.5176	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41383515:A:G	rs2004000	intron variant	G	4.18E-01	2.11E-07	0.3654	0.4180	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41376734:C:T	rs9549291	intron variant	T	4.03E-01	2.41E-07	0.3510	0.4030	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41384156:A:G	rs9549293	3 prime UTR variant	G	4.05E-01	2.45E-07	0.3530	0.4050	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	7.959
13:41384318:A:G	rs7322603	upstream gene variant	G	4.05E-01	2.58E-07	0.3531	0.4050				
13:41384382:C:T	rs7321976	upstream gene variant	T	4.04E-01	2.94E-07	0.3530	0.4047				
13:41376750:C:T	rs34320051	intron variant	T	4.02E-01	3.11E-07	0.3508	0.4023	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41369658:C:T	rs1536805	intron variant	T	4.03E-01	3.15E-07	0.3518	0.4034	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41376142:A:G	rs9549290	intron variant	G	4.15E-01	3.30E-07	0.3640	0.4157	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41377874:C:T	rs9549292	intron variant	T	4.15E-01	3.35E-07	0.3640	0.4157	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41382807:T:C	rs60754171	intron variant	C	4.04E-01	3.37E-07	0.3526	0.4040	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41369186:G:T	rs9549287	intron variant	T	4.03E-01	3.42E-07	0.3519	0.4033	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41374186:T:C	rs2282022	intron variant	C	4.15E-01	3.43E-07	0.3640	0.4156	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41380453:A:G	rs3783163	intron variant	G	4.03E-01	3.51E-07	0.3522	0.4036	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41372944:C:T	rs2297013	intron variant	T	4.03E-01	3.92E-07	0.3523	0.4034	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41372100:T:C	rs9603791	intron variant	C	4.03E-01	3.96E-07	0.3523	0.4035	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41371788:A:G	rs2297012	intron variant	G	4.03E-01	3.98E-07	0.3523	0.4034	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	5.853
13:41369731:A:C	rs1536806	intron variant	C	4.03E-01	4.01E-07	0.3523	0.4034	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41374834:G:A	rs2282024	intron variant	A	4.03E-01	4.04E-07	0.3523	0.4034	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41369340:C:T	rs9549288	intron variant	T	4.03E-01	4.04E-07	0.3524	0.4034	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	

13:41368989:C:A	rs12428672	intron variant	A	4.03E-01	4.04E-07	0.3524	0.4034	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	
13:41370122:A:G	rs1536808	intron variant	G	4.03E-01	4.07E-07	0.3524	0.4035	ENSG00000102743.10	protein coding	SLC25A15	7.797
13:41387996:T:C	rs1854420	downstream gene variant	C	4.09E-01	4.74E-07	0.3590	0.4098				5.100

Table 12. Phenotype 20002_1482 (chronic fatigue syndrome), females. From lowest p value to highest. n cases = 1208, n controls = 192945. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page.

variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
16:79293242:C:T	rs117712647	intergenic variant	T	7.28E-02	7.81E-08	0.1179	0.0726				
7:116165233:C:T	rs45498702	synonymous variant	T	5.13E-02	3.97E-07	0.0886	0.0512	ENSG00000105974.7	protein coding	CAV1	8.827

Table 13. Phenotype 20002_1482 (chronic fatigue syndrome), males. From lowest p value to highest. n cases = 451, n controls = 166537. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page.

variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
7:138607433:T:C	rs73729964	intron variant	C	9.57E-02	2.14E-07	0.1400	0.0956	ENSG00000122778.5	protein coding	KIAA1549	
7:138617682:C:T	rs17160621	intron variant	T	9.68E-02	2.41E-07	0.1412	0.0967	ENSG00000122778.5	protein coding	KIAA1549	
7:138615432:A:G	rs79520825	intron variant	G	9.68E-02	3.26E-07	0.1408	0.0967	ENSG00000122778.5	protein coding	KIAA1549	6.213
7:138611042:C:CT	rs533518051	intron variant	CT	1.08E-01	3.31E-07	0.1533	0.1077	ENSG00000122778.5	protein coding	KIAA1549	
7:138622642:G:A	rs73478201	intron variant	A	9.28E-02	3.39E-07	0.1358	0.0927	ENSG00000122778.5	protein coding	KIAA1549	
7:138617145:G:GA	rs145468320	intron variant	GA	9.65E-02	3.58E-07	0.1402	0.0964	ENSG00000122778.5	protein coding	KIAA1549	

Table 14. Phenotype R53 (fatigue and malaise), both sexes. From lowest p value to highest. n cases = 818, n controls = 360376. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page.

variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
12:48027306:TCA:T	rs778192622	intergenic variant	T	1.45E-01	1.38E-07	0.2144	0.1448				
3:13538079:C:G	rs2290195	intron variant	G	2.34E-01	4.03E-07	0.1731	0.2346	ENSG00000163517.10	protein coding	HDAC11	5.388
12:48144634:T:TG	rs5798039	intron variant	TG	1.39E-01	4.47E-07	0.2050	0.1388	ENSG00000079337.11	protein coding	RAPGEF3	
4:102544950:G:A	rs7677529	intron variant	A	3.67E-01	4.50E-07	0.3039	0.3669	ENSG00000153064.7	protein coding	BANK1	
12:48143978:C:T	rs12423645	intron variant	T	1.39E-01	4.58E-07	0.2050	0.1388	ENSG00000079337.11	protein coding	RAPGEF3	
7:138607433:T:C	rs73729964	intron variant	C	9.60E-02	4.85E-07	0.1502	0.0958	ENSG00000122778.5	protein coding	KIAA1549	
12:48142343:T:C	rs12424297	non coding transcript exon variant	C	1.39E-01	4.97E-07	0.2050	0.1389	ENSG00000079337.11	protein coding	RAPGEF3	7.588

Table 15. Phenotype R53 (fatigue and malaise), females. From lowest p value to highest. n cases = 456, n controls = 193718. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page.

variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
18:55454761:G:A	rs62092652	intron variant	A	2.42E-01	4.52E-08	0.3501	0.2422	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
18:55456674:G:A	rs2571236	intron variant	A	2.39E-01	6.02E-08	0.3450	0.2386	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
18:55455694:T:C	rs2663855	intron variant	C	2.46E-01	6.90E-08	0.3536	0.2459	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
18:55460012:C:CA	rs112376776	intron variant	CA	3.04E-01	9.20E-08	0.4210	0.3036	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
18:55453784:A:G	rs2850243	intron variant	G	3.05E-01	1.04E-07	0.4219	0.3043	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
18:55454080:A:G	rs2850244	intron variant	G	3.04E-01	1.32E-07	0.4206	0.3038	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
18:55458827:C:T	rs2663854	intron variant	T	3.03E-01	1.90E-07	0.4180	0.3026	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
18:55452281:T:C	rs2571227	intron variant	C	3.13E-01	1.92E-07	0.4301	0.3130	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
7:5211829:G:T	rs6463307	intergenic variant	G	3.81E-01	2.15E-07	0.5705	0.6190				
18:55452983:A:C	rs2571234	intron variant	C	3.10E-01	2.25E-07	0.4255	0.3095	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
18:55452554:A:G	rs7240802	intron variant	G	3.09E-01	2.27E-07	0.4249	0.3090	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	12.16
7:5211610:G:A	rs6463305	intergenic variant	G	3.81E-01	3.00E-07	0.5716	0.6189				
18:55459217:A:G	rs2663853	intron variant	G	3.03E-01	3.13E-07	0.4171	0.3031	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
7:5267524:C:T	rs4720539	intron variant	C	4.13E-01	4.20E-07	0.5364	0.5869	ENSG00000157954.10	protein coding	WIPI2	
18:55460845:C:T	rs2663851	intron variant	T	3.02E-01	4.57E-07	0.4130	0.3021	ENSG00000081923.6	protein coding	ATP8B1	
12:98200219:C:T	rs118022002	intergenic variant	T	5.48E-02	4.62E-07	0.1030	0.0547				

Table 16. Phenotype R53 (fatigue and malaise), males. From lowest p value to highest. n cases = 362, n controls = 166658. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page.

variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
14:47939323:AT:A	rs201706704	intron variant	AT	4.37E-01	1.08E-07	0.4735	0.5627	ENSG00000139915.14 ENSG00000272781.1	protein coding	MDGA2 MDGA2	
22:49865882:C:T	rs1534878	intron variant	T	8.74E-02	4.11E-07	0.1350	0.0873	ENSG00000188511.8	protein coding	C22orf34	
3:65411451:A:G	rs4583574	intron variant	G	2.32E-01	4.57E-07	0.1621	0.2327	ENSG00000151276.19	protein coding	MAGI1	

Table 17. Phenotype 20002_1542 (fibromyalgia), females only. From lowest p value to highest. n cases = 463, n controls = 193690. The first variant is included in two overlapping genes with same name but different gene id on h19. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page.

variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
7:70658177:C:T	rs1202660	intron variant	T	2.14E-01	3.53E-08	0.3187	0.213	ENSG00000185274.7	protein coding	WBSCR17	
9:29237269:C:T	rs75051717	intergenic variant	T	5.62E-02	4.71E-08	0.1146	0.0559				6.681

Table 18. Phenotype 20126_2 (bipolar II), females only. From lowest p value to highest. n cases = 233, n controls = 45475. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page.

variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
10:11889850:T:C	rs117238864	Intron variant	C	5.06E-02	1.40E-08	0.1036	0.0503	ENSG00000148426.8	protein coding	PROSER2	

Table 19. Phenotype 20126_2 (bipolar II), males only. From lowest p value to highest. n cases = 275, n controls = 40912. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page.

variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
4:136774175:A:G	rs4864302	intergenic variant	A	2.43E-01	2.43E-07	0.8192	0.7565				
4:136773892:T:G	rs4864299	intergenic variant	T	2.43E-01	2.53E-07	0.8192	0.7566				
4:136774148:G:A	rs4864301	intergenic variant	G	2.43E-01	2.63E-07	0.8192	0.7567				5.509
4:136768203:C:T	rs4404609	intergenic variant	C	2.44E-01	3.04E-07	0.8183	0.7561				

Table 20. Phenotype F5_DEPRESSIO (depression), females only. From lowest p value to highest. n cases = 630, n controls = 193544. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page.

variant	rsid	consequence	mA	min_AF	pval	Alt_AF cases	Alt_AF controls	gene_id	gene type	gene name	C score
5:5099922:C:T	rs62338016	intergenic variant	T	9.21E-02	1.03E-07	0.1392	0.0920				

Table 21. Phenotype F5_DEPRESSIO (depression), males only. n cases = 515, n controls = 166505. Only C scores above 5 have been reported. Click on gene name to open the relative NCBI page.

Chr	Pos	dbSNP	Cons	Gene/Gene ID	Ref	Alt	Trait	Sex	Beta	<i>p value</i>	MAF	MA	Reg.DB
10	131677233	rs148723539	intron 6/15	EBF3 ENSG00000108001	G	A	CFS	M+F	$5.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	A	5
13	41404706	rs11147812	intron 3/3	TPTE2P5 ENSG00000168852	T	C		F	$-1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$4.9 \cdot 10^{-1}$	C	7
7	56492485	rs182581502	intron 3/4	RP13-492C18.2 ENSG00000237268	G	T	CF	F	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-2}$	T	7
18	55454761	rs62092652	intron 1/27	ATP8B1 ENSG00000081923	G	A		M	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-1}$	A	4

Table 22. Genetic predisposition to Chronic Fatigue Syndrome and Chronic Fatigue (ICD10:R53), according to the metadata generated by Neale's lab from the dataset of the UK Biobank. Reg.DB stands for RegulomeDB and the scores are as follows: 4 = TF binding + DNase peak; 5 = TF binding or DNase peak; 7 = other TF binding evidence. The colored alleles are those associated with the trait (remember that a positive beta indicates association with the alternative allele, and a negative one indicates association with the reference allele). MAF is the minor allele frequency in the total sample, MA is the minor allele. Reference genome: GRCh37.

Chr	Pos	Region	dbSNP	Cons	Gene
10	131677233	10:131677015:G:C	rs185555709	intron	EBF3
		10:131677427:C:A	rs111625170	intron	
13	41404706	13:41404370:G:A	-	intron	TPTE2P5
		13:41404967:T:G	rs533184773	intron	
7	56492485	7:56492334:A:G	rs535554316	splice site	RP13-492C18.2
		7:56492503:T:TA	rs545368026	intron	
18	55454761	18:55454377:G:A	rs10503019	intron	ATP8B1
		18:55455373:T:A	rs556416375	intron	

Table 23. For each one of the variants of Table 22, I collect here the two closest positions genotyped in the Neale's Lab metadata.

4 Methods and theoretical background

4.1 Input files and where to download them

The collection of the analysis generated by Neale's Lab with the UK Biobank data is available [here](#). In line 2 of that file, you can download an explanation of the labels ([README](#)). On lines 8, 9, and 10 you can download a collection of the phenotypes and some of the attributes of the relative sample, for both sexes, females, and males respectively ([phenotypes.both sexes.tsv](#), [phenotypes.female.tsv](#), [phenotypes.male.tsv](#)). We are interested in phenotype 20002_1482 (Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome). In line 11 you find a file that contains the details on each variant ([variants.tsv](#)). These files must be unzipped before reading them. I placed the unzipped input files in the folder Genetics\Neale's Lab Metadata, while all the zipped files are in the folder Genetics\Neale's Lab Meta data\Original zipped files.

	A	B	C	...
A1	variant	Chr	pos	...
A2	1:15791:C:T	1	15791	...
:	:	:	:	:
A13364304	22:51237712:G:A	22	51237712	...
A13364305	X:2699555:C:A	X	2699555	...
:	:	:	:	:
A13791470	X:154930487:T:A	X	154930487	...

Table 24. Structure of the first three columns of variants.tsv. This file includes a total of 213 columns and of 13,791,470 lines.

4.1.1 File variants.tsv

File variants.tsv has 13,791,468 lines and 25 columns. It can't be opened by using Excel. My advice is to use EmEditor (both the professional version and the free version will do for just reading the content). The number of lines of variants.tsv is the number of variants included in the analysis, plus one (because one line goes for the labels). It includes 13,364,303 variants for autosomes. From line A13364305 to line A13791470 we have further 427,166 variants on chromosome X; no variants on chromosome Y are included in this analysis (see Table 24).

variant	Variant identifier in the form "chr:pos:ref:alt", where "ref" is aligned to the forward strand.
chr	Chromosome of the variant.
pos	Position of the variant in GRCh37 coordinates.
ref	Reference allele on the forward strand.
alt	Alternate allele (not necessarily minor allele).
rsid	rsid (not guaranteed to be unique).
varid	Unique variant identifier included in imputed BGEN files.
consequence	Consequence annotated using VEP version 85.
consequence_category	Category of VEP-annotated consequence ("ptv", "missense", "synonymous", "non_coding").

info	Imputation INFO score as provided by UK Biobank.
call_rate	Call rate (calculated using hardcall ¹ genotypes).
AC	Alt allele count (calculated using hardcall genotypes).
AF	Alt ² allele frequency (calculated using hardcall genotypes).
minor_allele	Minor allele (equal to ref allele when AF > 0.5, otherwise equal to alt allele).
minor_AF	Minor allele frequency calculated using hardcall genotypes on n_called.
p_hwe	Hardy-Weinberg p-value.
n_called	Number of samples with defined genotype at this variant.
n_not_called	Number of samples without a defined genotype at this variant.
n_hom_ref	Number of samples with homozygous reference genotype at this variant.
n_het	Number of samples with heterozygous genotype at this variant.
n_hom_var	Number of samples with homozygous alternate genotype at this variant.
n_non_ref	Number of samples with non-homozygous reference genotype at this variant (n_het + n_hom_var)
r_heterozygosity	Proportion of samples with heterozygous genotype at this variant.
r_het_hom_var	Ratio of samples with heterozygous genotype to samples with homozygous alternate genotype at this variant.
r_expected_het_frequency	Expected r_heterozygosity based on Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium.

Table 25. Labels of each column of variants.tsv, and their meanings.

4.1.1.1 Variants annotation

The explanation for the meaning of the label of each column is included in the already mentioned README file, but I have collected them in Table 25 with only minor changes, to enhance clarity. Each variant has its VEP-annotated consequence and the various consequences have been collected under four big categories, according to the scheme in Table 26.

I built this table by direct inspection of variants.tsv: by using EmEditor I have selected all the lines corresponding to the value missense in column consequence_category, then I copied column consequence in another file and I have eliminated duplicated lines. This gives a list of the consequences for missense. I have then repeated the same algorithm for the remaining three consequence categories. For a description of the meaning of the labels in the central column of the table, please visit [this page](#) on Ensemble's website. The left column is taken from the mentioned page and the meaning of the attributes is as follows:

1. HIGH: the variant is assumed to have a high (disruptive) impact on the protein, probably causing protein truncation, loss of function, or triggering nonsense-mediated decay;
2. MODERATE: a non-disruptive variant that might change protein effectiveness;

¹ Hardcall genotype values means: 0/1/2 for hom_Ref/het/hom_Var (R).

² The fact that AC and AF both refer to the alternate allele is indicated in the FAQ page of Neale Lab (R).

3. LOW: assumed to be mostly harmless or unlikely to change protein behavior;
4. MODIFIER: usually non-coding variants or variants affecting non-coding genes, where predictions are difficult or there is no evidence of impact.

impact	consequence	consequence category	number of variants		
			1-22	X	tot
MODERATE	inframe_deletion	missense	192,317	3,044	195,361
MODERATE	inframe_insertion				
MODERATE	missense_variant				
MODERATE	protein_altering_variant				
LOW	splice_region_variant				
HIGH	start_lost				
HIGH	stop_lost				
HIGH	frameshift_variant	ptv	9,669	115	9,784
HIGH	splice_acceptor_variant				
HIGH	splice_donor_variant				
HIGH	stop_gained				
LOW	incomplete_terminal_codon_variant	synonymous	106,892	1,877	108,769
LOW	stop_retained_variant				
LOW	synonymous_variant				
MODIFIER	upstream_gene_variant	non_coding	13,055,425	422,128	13,477,553
MODIFIER	intron_variant				
MODIFIER	non_coding_transcript_exon_variant				
MODIFIER	downstream_gene_variant				
MODIFIER	intergenic_variant				
MODIFIER	3_prime_UTR_variant				
MODIFIER	5_prime_UTR_variant				
MODIFIER	regulatory_region_variant				
MODIFIER	TF_binding_site_variant				
MODIFIER	mature_miRNA_variant				
MODIFIER	TFBS_ablation				
MODIFIER	coding_sequence_variant				
MODIFIER	non_coding_transcript_variant				

Table 26. Each variant has its VEP-annotated consequence and the various consequences have been collected under four big categories, according to the scheme in this table. I have also indicated the total number of variants for each consequence category, their number within the autosomes (1-22), and how many of them fall in the X chromosome.

4.1.1.2 Alternative allele, reference allele, and minor allele

As a further note, AC and AF are the alternative allele count and frequency, respectively, among the sample n_{called} which is of a total of 361,194 individuals. The count is made by a method called hardcall: at a given variant, we had 2 to AC if we have an individual who is homozygous for the

alternative allele (hom_Var), we had 1 if the individual is heterozygous (het), we had zero in case of homozygosity for the reference allele (hom_Var) (R). Then we calculate:

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad \text{AF} = \frac{\text{AC}}{\text{n_called}} = \frac{\text{AC}}{361194}$$

Note that AF is the alternative allele frequency. When $\text{AF} > 0$, it is also the frequency of the major allele and, in this case, $\text{minor_AF} = 1.0 - \text{AF}$ (Table 27).

CASES	Alternative allele frequency	Major allele frequency	Minor allele frequency	
$\text{AF} > 0.5$	AF	AF	$\text{minor_AF} = 1.0 - \text{AF}$	alternative allele = major allele reference allele = minor allele
$\text{AF} < 0.5$	AF	-	AF	alternative allele = minor allele reference allele = major allele

Table 27. AF is the alternative allele frequency. When $\text{AF} > 0$, it is also the frequency of the major allele and in this case $\text{minor_AF} = 1.0 - \text{AF}$.

4.1.2 File imputed_both_sexes.tsv

On line 1368 of the already mentioned page with the collection of Neale's lab metadata ([here](#)), we find the genetic data for the group of patients of both sexes with the phenotype 20002_1482 (Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome). The original name of the file is 20002_1482.gwas.imputed_v3.both_sexes.tsv.bgz. In what follows it will simply be referred to by the name 20002_1482_imputed_both_sexes.tsv.

Note also that a description of the meaning of the labels of the column of this file is included in the already mentioned README, but I have collected them in Table 25 with only minor changes, to enhance clarity.

variant	Variant identifier in the form "chr:pos:ref:alt", where "ref" is aligned to the forward strand of GRCh37 and "alt" is the effect allele (use this to join with variant annotation file).
minor_allele	The minor allele (alt allele is not always minor).
minor_AF	Frequency of the minor allele in the n_complete_samples defined for this phenotype.
expected_case_minor_AC	(Optional) For case/control phenotypes, calculated as $(2 * \text{minor_AF} * \text{n_cases})$.
expected_min_category_minor_AC	(Optional) For categorical phenotypes with less than 5 categories, calculated as $(2 * \text{minor_AF} * \text{number of samples in smallest category})$.
low_confidence_variant	Flag indicating low confidence results based on the following heuristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case/control phenotypes: $\text{expected_case_minor_AC} < 25$ or $\text{minor_AF} < 0.001$. - Categorical phenotypes with less than 5 categories: $\text{expected_min_category_minor_AC} < 25$ or $\text{minor_AF} < 0.001$. - Quantitative phenotypes: $\text{minor_AF} < 0.001$.

n_complete_samples	Number of samples defined for this phenotype and sex (cases + controls).
AC	Allele count of alt allele calculated on dosages within n_complete_samples.
ytx	Alt allele count in cases.
beta	Estimated effect size of alt allele.
se	Estimated standard error of beta.
tstat	t-statistic of beta estimate (= beta/se).
pval	p-value of beta significance test.

Table 28. Labels of each column of 20002_1482.gwas.imputed_v3.both_sexes.tsv.bgz, and their meanings.

4.1.2.1 Alternative allele, reference allele, and minor allele

As you can see, several labels of this file have the same name as some of the labels already seen in variants.tsv. But while the label variant indicates the same object in both cases, the others do not. In particular, AC is the alternative allele³ count in n_complete_samples, which is the total size (cases plus controls) for the phenotype considered. This number can be retrieved from the file phenotypes.both_sexes.tsv along with the values n_cases, n_controls. I report these values in Table 29, not only for both sexes but also for females and males.

Note that by adding the first two columns of Table 29 cell by cell, you get the third one; by adding the first two lines you get the third one. Then, in this case, we have

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad \text{minor_AF} = \begin{cases} \frac{AC}{n_complete_samples} = \frac{AC}{361194} & \text{if } AF \leq 0.5 \\ 1 - \frac{AC}{n_complete_samples} & \text{if } AF > 0.5 \end{cases}$$

	n_cases	n_controls	n_complete_samples
females	1208	192945	194153
males	451	166537	166988
both_sexes	1659	359482	361141

Table 29. The number of cases, controls, and total sample, for phenotype 20002_1482 (chronic fatigue syndrome).

4.1.3 Phenotypes considered

The phenotypes that are included in the UK Biobank database are collected in the following files: phenotypes.both_sexes.tsv, phenotypes.female.tsv, phenotypes.male.tsv

Click on the names of the files to download them. They can be found on lines 8, 9, 10 of the main page of Neale's Lab with the UK Biobank data ([here](#)).

³ Note that the alternative allele for any given variant is defined by the reference genome of choice (h19, in this case) so it never changes, no matter the sample or file we are considering.

phenotype	description	source	n_controls	n_cases	sex
20002_1482	Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome	phesant	359482	1659	B
			192945	1208	F
			166537	451	M
R53	Diagnoses - main ICD10: R53 Malaise and fatigue	icd10	360376	818	B
			193718	456	F
			166658	362	M
20002_1542	Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: fibromyalgia	phesant	360608	533	B
			193690	463	F
			-	-	M
20126_2	Bipolar and major depression status: Bipolar II Disorder	phesant	86387	508	B
			45475	233	F
			40912	275	M
I95	Diagnoses - main ICD10: I95 Hypotension	icd10	360628	566	B
			193966	208	F
			166662	358	M
F5_DEPRESSIO	Depression	finngen	360049	1145	B
			193544	630	F
			166505	515	M

Table 30. The phenotype considered in my analysis. Click to the ICD10 code of a diagnosis (when present) to read a description. B: both sexes; F: females; M: males. A relaxed cut-off for statistical significance (par. 4.6.4, 4.6.5) will be applied only to phenotypes shaded green.

As for the column about phenotype's source, note that:

1. finngen: These phenotypes were manually curated by collaborators in the FinnGen research project. Many are combinations of different ICD10 codes.
2. phesant: These phenotypes were automatically processed using a modified version of the software PHESANT ([Ref](#)).

I searched in the first one with the following keywords: fatigue, myalgic, encephalomyelitis, fibromyalgia, post, post-viral, hypermobility, Ehlers-Danlos, Ehlers, Danlos, EDS, Q fever, Q-fever, POTS, tachycardia, dysautonomia, dysautonomic, autonomic, hypotension, Lyme. I also included the key word 'depression', 'affective', and 'apathy', for control groups. I retrieved the phenotypes of interest collected in Table 30.

4.2 Generating the output

Note that phenotype_imputed_sex.tsv stands for phenotype.gwas.imputed_v3.sex.tsv, the original designation of the file by Neale's lab, where phenotype is the code of the phenotype we are considering (for instance, 20002_1482 for Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome) and the string sex can have the values: both_sexes, female, male.

4.2.1 Filtering

1. Open phenotype_imputed_sex.tsv and insert at columns 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 columns 2, 3, 6, 8, 9 from variants.tsv, respectively. It must be done one column at a time and even by doing so, the process requires some minutes for each column. I insert an empty column in phenotype_imputed_sex.tsv before pasting a column from variants.tsv, I don't know if it is necessary or not. This file can be saved as phenotype_imputed_sex_edited.txt if you plan to perform filtering with different criteria.
2. Filtering by p-value: positive filter, number range [0, 5.e-7], for column 17. Save the result of filtering with the command extract all, then add the headings (copy from phenotype_imputed_sex.tsv after removing the filter), then save as phenotype_filtered_sex.txt.
3. Filtering by MAF: negative filter, number range [0,0.05], for column 8. Then export and save (as above) over phenotype_filtered_sex.txt.
4. I have checked if the selected variants were in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) in the total sample by reading column 16 of variants.tsv following the rule of considering a sign of genotyping error the HWE p value below 10^{-6} (Marees AT et al. 2018). To do so, I selected from variants.tsv the about 41320 variants with an HWE p value below 10^{-6} and then I compared them with the select variants: none of the variants collected had an HWE p value below the cut-off (see par. 4.6.6).

4.2.2 Calculating allele frequencies

We open phenotype_filtered_sex.txt with Excel and calculate, for each variant, the frequencies of alternative alleles in both cases and controls, by following the algorithm shown in this paragraph where we perform by hand this operation for only one variant, the one in Table 32.

Since $AF = 0.505594 > 0.5$, we have that in this case, the alternative allele (A) is the major allele. As a consequence, the reference allele (G) is the minor allele.

We can also say that the frequency of the minor allele is $1 - 0.505594 = 0,494406$ and this is because in the present analysis we always assume only two alleles at each position. For this position, we have the values collected in Table 31 where I have not only included those for both sexes (retrieved from phenotype_imputed_sex.tsv) but also those for females only and males only.

As mentioned, the minor allele G is the reference one, in this case, so if we assumed the same frequency for the minor allele in both cases and control we would have a frequency for G among cases given by

$$\text{minor_AF} \times n_{\text{cases}} \times 2 = 0.494397 \times 1659 \times 2 = 1640.41$$

which is exactly the value of expected_case_minor_AC (rounded at the second decimal digit). The number of alternative alleles in cases is ytx, then the frequency of the alternative and major allele A among cases is given by

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad f_{\text{cases}}(\text{alt}) = \frac{ytx}{n_{\text{cases}} \times 2} = \frac{1541}{1659 \times 2} = 0,464436$$

Which means that

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad f_{\text{cases}}(\text{ref}) = 1 - f_{\text{cases}}(\text{alt}) = 0,535563$$

For the control group we have

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad f_{controls}(alt) = \frac{AC-ytx}{n_{controls} \times 2} = \frac{365188-1541}{359482 \times 2} = 0,505793$$

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad f_{controls}(ref) = 1 - f_{controls}(alt) = 0,494206$$

We can then find the missing allele counts easily from the ones we already know. Hence, the allele count for the reference allele among cases and controls is given respectively by

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad count_{cases}(ref) = n_{cases} \times 2 - ytx = 1777$$

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad count_{controls}(ref) = n_{controls} \times 2 - (AC - ytx) = 355317$$

where we have considered also that

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad count_{controls}(alt) = AC - ytx = 363647$$

Label	Both sexes	Females	Males
minor_AF	0.494397	0.494672	0.494077
expected_case_minor_AC	1640.41	1195.13	445.658
n_complete_samples	361141	194153	166988
AC	365188	196222	168966
ytx	1541	1082	459
pval	$3.95570 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2.55504 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.774073

Table 31. Genetic data for all the sex groups for phenotype 20002_1482 (Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome) for the variant we are interested in.

Label	Variant details
variant	13:41353297:G:A
rsid	rs7337312
varid	rs7337312
ref	G
alt	A
consequence	regulatory_region_variant
consequence_category	non_coding
AC	365235
AF ⁴	0.505594
minor_allele	G
minor_AF	0.494406
n_called	361194
n_not_called	0

Table 32. In the third column some of the details for the variant we are interested in, from the variants.tsv file. The column on the center collects the explanations of the labels, from the README file.

⁴ When AF>0.5 then the alternative allele is the major allele, while the reference allele is the minor allele (see also Table 27).

This leads to the values in Table 33. And this is the general algorithm followed for building the output file, starting from variants.tsv and imputed_both_sexes.tsv (plus the numbers n_cases, n_controls retrieved from phenotypes.both_sexes.tsv at line 2304 (line 3 of Table 29). This general method is also summarized in Table 34.

Groups	N	Allele A (Alt, Major)		Allele G (Ref, Minor)	
		count	frequency	count	frequency
Cases	1659	1541	0,464436	1777	0,535563
Controls	359482	363647	0,505793	355317	0,494206

Table 33. Frequencies and allele count for both cases and controls (phenotype 20002_1482, both sexes).

Groups	N	Alt Allele		Ref Allele	
		count	frequency	count	frequency
Cases	n_cases	ytx	$\frac{ytx}{n_cases \times 2}$	$n_cases \times 2 - ytx$	$1 - \frac{ytx}{n_cases \times 2}$
Controls	n_controls	AC - ytx	$\frac{AC - ytx}{n_controls \times 2}$	$n_controls \times 2 - (AC - ytx)$	$1 - \frac{AC - ytx}{n_controls \times 2}$

Table 34. The general method for calculating frequencies and allele counts for both cases and controls. Note that n_cases, n_controls are retrieved from phenotypes.both_sexes.tsv at line 2304 and are always the same, while ytx, AC are retrieved from imputed_both_sexes.tsv for each variant.

Once we have calculated the cells for alt allele frequency, we save the file in .xlsx format. So we end up with the following three files for each phenotype:

phenotype_filtered_sex.xlsx, sex = both_sexes, female, male

4.2.3 Assigning each variant to its gene (if any)

Once filtered the variants and calculated their frequencies in cases and controls, we are also interested in assigning each one of them to its gene (when possible). To do so we need a list of the starting position and ending position for each human gene, within the reference genome of choice (h19 alias GRCh37). This means that we need a script for writing such a list in a suitable form and one that uses this list for associating each variant of filtered_autosomes_both_sexes_THRESHOLD.csv to its gene (if any).

4.2.3.1 Writing a list of human genes and their positions

We start from the zipped file gencode.v19.annotation.gtf ([download](#)), retrieved from the page of genecodegenes.org dedicated to GRCh37 ([link](#)). Once unzipped, I saved it as xlsx file with the name gencode_v19_annotation_genes_only.xlsx. This file is read by the script in par. 4.2.3.1.1, called gene_list_autosomes.m. In particular, it reads It reads columns A (chromosome), D (starting position), E (ending position), I (gene_id), K (gene_type), M (gene_name). It then writes these columns in a new file, called hg19_genes_autosomes.csv. The first lines of this file are collected in Table 35 as an example. Note that the elements of column 5 overlap along the genome. The meanings of the labels in column 5 can be found on [this page](#).

Chr	starting pos	ending pos	gene_id	gene_type	gene_name
1	11869	14412	ENSG00000223972.4	pseudogene	DDX11L1
1	14363	29806	ENSG00000227232.4	pseudogene	WASH7P
1	29554	31109	ENSG00000243485.2	lincRNA	MIR1302-11
1	34554	36081	ENSG00000237613.2	lincRNA	FAM138A
1	52473	54936	ENSG00000268020.2	pseudogene	OR4G4P
1	62948	63887	ENSG00000240361.1	pseudogene	OR4G11P
1	69091	70008	ENSG00000186092.4	protein_coding	OR4F5
1	89295	133566	ENSG00000238009.2	lincRNA	RP11-34P13.7
1	89551	91105	ENSG00000239945.1	lincRNA	RP11-34P13.8
1	131025	134836	ENSG00000233750.3	pseudogene	CICP27

Table 35. First lines of the file hg19_genes_autosomes.csv.

4.2.3.1.1 Script

All the scripts presented in this document are written in GNU Octave, version 6.3.0.

```

% file name = gene_list_autosomes
clear all
close all
pkg load io % see https://octave.sourceforge.io/io/ for a description of pkg
tic % start counting execution time (seconds)
%-----
n = 54849 % lines of gencode_v19_annotation_genes_only.xlsx for autosomes
strn = num2str(n); % conversion to string of the number of lines
file_name = 'gencode_v19_annotation_genes_only.xlsx'
sheet = 'genes'
%-----
% It reads column A and transforms it from chrn to n format, where n is the number
% of the chromosome
%-----
range = strcat('A1:A',strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
temp = text; % temp is a cell array containing column A1:An
% We convert each cell to string from position 4
% then we transform the string to a number and store it in chr
for i = 1:n
    chr (i) = str2num(substr(char(temp(i)),4));
endfor
%-----
% It reads columns D (starting position), E (ending position)
%-----
range = strcat('D1:D',strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
s_pos = num;
range = strcat('E1:E',strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
e_pos = num;
%-----
% It reads I (gene_id)
%-----
range = strcat('I1:I',strn)

```

```

[num,text,raw,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
temp = text;
gene_id = cell (n,1);
for i = 1:n
    gene_id (i) = substr(char(temp(i)),10);          % this does not include: gene_id "
    tok = strtok (char(gene_id (i)), "");          % we remove the second "
    gene_id (i) = tok;
endfor
%
execution_time = strcat(num2str(toc/60)," minutes")    % execution time
%-----
% It reads K (gene_type)
%-----
range = strcat('K1:K',strn)
[num,text,raw,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
temp = text;
gene_type = cell (n,1);
for i = 1:n
    gene_type (i) = substr(char(temp(i)),12);        % this does not include: gene_id "
    tok = strtok (char(gene_type (i)), "");        % we remove the second "
    gene_type (i) = tok;
endfor
%-----
% It reads M (gene_name)
%-----
range = strcat('M1:M',strn)
[num,text,raw,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
temp = text;
gene_name = cell (n,1);
for i = 1:n
    gene_name (i) = substr(char(temp(i)),12);      % this does not include: gene_id "
    tok = strtok (char(gene_name (i)), "");      % we remove the second "
    gene_name (i) = tok;
endfor
%-----
% we now build for each array a cell array with heading
%-----
cell_array = cell (n+1,6);
cell_array {1,1} = "Chr";
cell_array {1,2} = "starting pos";
cell_array {1,3} = "ending pos";
cell_array {1,4} = "gene_id";
cell_array {1,5} = "gene_type";
cell_array {1,6} = "gene_name";
%-----
for i=1:n
    cell_array {i+1,1} = chr(i);
    cell_array {i+1,2} = s_pos(i);
    cell_array {i+1,3} = e_pos(i);
    cell_array {i+1,4} = char(gene_id(i));
    cell_array {i+1,5} = char(gene_type(i));
    cell_array {i+1,6} = char(gene_name(i));
endfor
%-----
% we now write the out put, called hg19_genes_autosomes.tsv
%-----
file_name = 'hg19_genes_autosomes.tsv';
cell2csv (file_name, cell_array, " ")

```

```
%-----
execution_time = strcat(num2str(toc/60)," minutes")    % execution time
```

4.2.3.2 Associating variants and genes

The script read columns A, B, C, D, E, and F of hg19_headers_autosomes.xlsx and also columns B, and C of filtered_autosomes_both_sexes.tsv and it assigns each variant of the latter to a gene from the former. It handles overlapping genes: if multiple genes are associated with the same variant, they are added on consecutive columns, at the same line, as they are identified. The output file is

filtered_autosomes_SEX_THRESHOLD_genes_over.csv

where SEX is replaced by both_sexes or females or males, and THRESHOLD is the number chosen as a cut-off for minor allele frequency.

4.2.3.2.1 Script

All the scripts presented in this document are written in GNU Octave, version 6.3.0.

```
% file name = genes
% date of creation = 25/09/2021
% this script read columns A, B, C, D, E, F of hg19_headers_autosomes.xlsx and
% also column B, C of filtered_autosomes_both_sexes.tsv and it assigns
% each variant of the latter to a gene from the former
% it handles overlapping genes
clear all
close all
pkg load io
tic                % we start counting execution time (seconds)
phenotype = '20002_1482'
sex = 'both_sexes'
%-----
% we read all columns of hg19_headers_autosomes.xlsx
%-----
file_name = "hg19_genes_autosomes.xlsx"
[filetype, sh_names, fformat, nmranges] = xlsfinfo (file_name);
strn = char(sh_names(1,2));
strn = substr(strn,5)           % upper limit for range as a string
m = str2num(strn)              % upper limit for range as a number
sheet = char(sh_names(1,1));   % name of the sheet
range = strcat("A2:A",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
chr_hg19 = num;
range = strcat("B2:B",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
s_pos_hg19 = num;
range = strcat("C2:C",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
e_pos_hg19 = num;
range = strcat("D2:D",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
gene_id = text;
range = strcat("E2:E",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
gene_type = text;
```

```

range = strcat("F2:F",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
gene_name = text;
%-----
% we read columns B, C from phenotype_filtered_sex.xlsx
%-----
file_name = strcat(phenotype,"_filtered_",sex,".xlsx")
[filetype, sh_names, fformat, nmranges] = xlsinfo (file_name);
strn = char(sh_names(1,2));
strn = substr(strn,5)           % upper limit for range as a string
lines_h = str2num(strn)        % upper limit for range as a number
sheet = char(sh_names(1,1));   % name of the sheet
range = strcat("B2:B",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
chr_autosomes = num;
range = strcat("C2:C",strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
pos_autosomes = num;
%-----
% we assign a gene to each variant in index_h, when possible
%-----
gene_h = cell(lines_h,3);
for i=1:lines_h - 1
    c(i) = 1;
    for j=1:m - 1
        if (and((chr_autosomes(i) == chr_hg19(j)),(pos_autosomes(i) >= s_pos_hg19(j)),(pos_autosomes(i)...
            <= e_pos_hg19(j))))
            gene_h {i+1,c(i)} = char(gene_id {j});
            gene_h {i+1,c(i)+1} = char(gene_type {j});
            gene_h {i+1,c(i)+2} = char(gene_name {j});
            c(i) = c(i) + 3;
        end
    end
endfor
col = max(c) - 3;
%-----
% we define the cell array that will contain the whole output of this script,
% including the headers
%-----
columns = cell(lines_h,col);
for j=1:3:col
    columns{1,j} = "gene_id";
    columns{1,j+1} = "gene_type";
    columns{1,j+2} = "gene_name";
endfor
%-----
% writing
%-----
for i=1:lines_h-1
    for j=1:3:col
        columns{i+1,j} = char (gene_h {i+1,j});
        columns{i+1,j+1} = char (gene_h {i+1,j+1});
        columns{i+1,j+2} = char (gene_h {i+1,j+2});
    endfor
endfor
strn = num2str(threshold)
file_name = strcat(phenotype,"_filtered_",sex,"_genes_over.csv");

```

```
cell2csv (file_name, columns," ")
execution_time = strcat(num2str(toc/3600)," hours")
```

4.3 Assigning a deleteriousness score (C-score) to statistical significant variants

4.3.1 CADD and C-score

Combined Annotation Dependent Depletion (CADD) is a tool for assigning to each human variant a score of deleteriousness (called C-score) based on the fate that a variant has been subjected to during human evolution from the common primate ancestor: those alleles that have been depleted in their frequency are likely to have been discarded by the pressure of selection because of their tendency to decrease the fitness of carriers. The algorithm that goes under the name of CADD compares the frequency of the alleles of each known human variant with both the genetic material belonging to the inferred human-chimpanzee ancestral genome and a simulation for random genetic events (Kircher, M. et al. 2014). The meaning of a C-score is as follows: if a variant has a C-score of x , then defined the value

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad p = 10^{-\frac{x}{10}}$$

we have that the variant is included among the pN_{tot} most deleterious variants, where N_{tot} is the total number of variants considered (~8.6 billion). As an example, if the score is 10, then the variant is among the 10% of N_{tot} with the highest level of deleteriousness; if the score is 20, then we have $p = 10^{-2}$ and the variant is included among the 1% of N_{tot} with the highest level of deleteriousness. And so forth. It must be added that the C-score we have here described is the scaled C-score, also designated as PHRED. A C-score ≥ 15 has been suggested to be pointing to possible pathogenicity (see [this page](#) as a reference and an introduction to CADD).

4.3.2 How to assign C-scores

To retrieve the C-score of a set of variants, we need to write them in VCF format (only the first five columns will do, no heading is necessary). For a description of this format, please visit [this link](#). The following table gives an example of what the first five columns of a VCA file look like. Note that “.” is used when a value is missing; note also the comma when multiple alternative alleles are present.

CHROM	POS	ID	REF	ALT
20	14370	rs6054257	G	A
20	17330	.	T	A
20	1110696	rs6040355	A	G,T

The document must be written as a .tsv file, with “\t” as a delimiter. The .tsv file must then be uploaded to this website: <https://cadd.gs.washington.edu/score> in order to assign a C-score to each variant. In our case, the coordinate system is GRCh37, hence I submitted the .tsv file to the GRCh37-v.1.6 version of CADD. I have noticed that for the same variant you can get a different C-score depending on whether the reference genome is GRCh37 or GRCh38. So, for instance, if we consider variant rs2017696, we have the two following coordinates depending on the reference genome used.

C-score, in this case, has been retrieved from the page: <https://cadd.gs.washington.edu/snv> (this service is very useful if you have to check the C-score of just a few variants). As you can see, the result is slightly different if we consider one reference genome instead of the other, for this variant.

Ref Genome	CHR	POS	ID	REF	ALT	C-score
GRCh37	13	41387065	rs2017696	T	A	5.023
GRCh38	13	40812929		T	A	4.145

4.3.3 Script

All the scripts presented in this document are written in GNU Octave, version 6.3.0.

```
% file name = significant_variants_2vcf
%
% date of creation = 21/03/2022
%
%-----
% Description
%-----
% It reads a list of variants from a xlsx file of two columns. The first column
% contains the variants in format chr:pos:ref:alt, the second column contains
% its rsid, when available, otherwise it contains the same value of the first column.
% It then writes a tsv file of five columns where for each variant we have the
% values: chr, pos, ref, alt, rsid (when available). If rsid is not available, it
% writes a dot: "."
%-----
clear all
close all
pkg load io % see https://octave.sourceforge.io/io/ for a description of pkg
tic % start counting execution time (seconds)
%-----
n = 81 % lines
strn = num2str(n); % conversion to string of the number of lines
file_name = 'significant_variants.xlsx'
sheet = "Sheet1"
%-----
% It reads column A
%-----
range = strcat('A1:A',strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
temp = text; % temp is a cell array containing column A1:An
%-----
% It reads the chromosome, the position, the reference allele, and the alternative
% allele for each variant and it stores it in the first column of cell_array
%-----
for i = 1:n
    cell_array {i,1} = strtok (char(temp{i}), ":"); % read temp{i} until the first ":" (chromosome)
    m = index (char(temp{i}), ":"); % the position of the first ":" along temp{i}
    temp{i} = substr (char(temp{i}), m+1); % read temp{i} from just after the first ":"
    cell_array {i,2} = strtok (char(temp{i}), ":"); % read the position
    m = index (char(temp{i}), ":");
    temp{i} = substr (char(temp{i}), m+1);
    cell_array {i,4} = strtok (char(temp{i}), ":"); % read the reference allele
    m = index (char(temp{i}), ":");
    temp{i} = substr (char(temp{i}), m+1);
    cell_array {i,5} = strtok (char(temp{i}), ":"); % read the alternative allele
endfor
%-----
% It reads column B
```

```

%-----
range = strcat('B1:B',strn)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread (file_name, sheet, range);
temp = text;
%-----
% It reads rsid for each variant. If it is the same as the variant itself (no rs id)
% it stores a dot (".")
%-----
for i = 1:n
    if ( strtrunc(char(temp{i}),2) != "rs" )
        cell_array {i,3} = ".";
    else
        cell_array {i,3} = char(temp{i});
    endif
endfor
%-----
% we now write the output
%-----
file_name = 'significant_variants.tsv';
cell2csv (file_name, cell_array,"\t")
%-----
execution_time = strcat(num2str(toc/60)," minutes")           % execution time

```

4.4 Interpretation of the results

For each variant selected by the filtering process described in par. 4.2.1 I searched for traits associated with a p value below $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ by all available GWAS studies, by manually interrogating the GWAS catalog at this link: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/home> (Buniello A et al. 2019). I made a similar search at a gene level, for all the genes including at least one variant selected by the filtering process (Table 2).

4.4.1 Searching for associations between variants and biomarkers within the UK Biobank

The list of biomarkers common for both sexes is the file:

biomarkers.both_sexes.tsv

Let us say that we are interested in Urea (mmol/L) in females from the UK population, then we download:

30670_raw.gwas.imputed_v3.female.varorder.tsv

We then apply the filtering described in par. 4.2.1 and we end up with a file that we save as

filtered_30670_raw.gwas.imputed_v3.female.varorder.txt

In this file, we can test whether the variants are associated with one of the phenotypes of par. 4.1.3 are associated with the biomarker considered too.

4.5 Distribution of minor allele frequency

The file `variants_min_AF_autosomes.csv` allows for building a plot for the distribution of the number of variants as a function of their minor allele frequency, as in Figure 4. This distribution follows the general shape already known for minor allele frequency in the context of human whole-genome sequencing (see [this reference](#)). It resembles an exponential distribution, but you can note that for very small minor allele frequency, the distribution decreases. This would suggest a beta distribution instead, as the following one:

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad f(\varphi) = C + A\varphi^{\alpha-1}(1-\varphi)^{\beta-1} \quad \forall \varphi \in [0, 0.5], \alpha > 1$$

where φ is minor allele frequency and $f(\varphi)d\varphi$ is the number of variants with a minor allele frequency between φ and $\varphi + d\varphi$. The parameters C, A, α, β must be identified by asking that $f(\varphi)$ verifies some attributes of the empirical distribution. We can for instance ask that the integral of $f(\varphi)$ in $[0, 0.5]$ is equal to N_L (the total number of variants genotyped), in other words, the following equation must be true

$$\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} f(\varphi) d\varphi = N_L \Leftrightarrow \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} C d\varphi + A \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi^{\alpha-1}(1-\varphi)^{\beta-1} d\varphi = N_L \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad \frac{C}{2} + B_{0.5}(\alpha, \beta)A = N_L$$

where $B_{0.5}(\alpha, \beta)$ is the incomplete beta function in $z = 0.5$, defined by

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad B_z(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^z \varphi^{\alpha-1}(1-\varphi)^{\beta-1} d\varphi$$

We can then ask that the first-order moment of $f(\varphi)$ in $[0, 0.5]$ is the same as the experimental one, that we'll indicate μ_1 , which leads to the condition

$$\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi f(\varphi) d\varphi = \mu_1 \Leftrightarrow C \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi d\varphi + A \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi^\alpha(1-\varphi)^{\beta-1} d\varphi = \mu_1 \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad \frac{C}{8} + B_{0.5}(\alpha + 1, \beta)A = \mu_1$$

As two further conditions, we ask for the moments of the second and third order to be the same in the theoretical distribution and the experimental one. For the second-order moment we have:

$$\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi^2 f(\varphi) d\varphi = \mu_2 \Leftrightarrow C \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi^2 d\varphi + A \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi^{\alpha+1}(1-\varphi)^{\beta-1} d\varphi = \mu_2 \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad \frac{C}{24} + B_{0.5}(\alpha + 2, \beta)A = \mu_2$$

For the third-order moment the condition is:

$$\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi^3 f(\varphi) d\varphi = \mu_3 \Leftrightarrow C \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi^3 d\varphi + A \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \varphi^{\alpha+2}(1-\varphi)^{\beta-1} d\varphi = \mu_3 \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad \frac{c}{64} + B_{0.5}(\alpha + 3, \beta)A = \mu_3$$

This leads to the non-linear system

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad \begin{cases} \frac{c}{2} + B_{0.5}(\alpha, \beta)A = N_L \\ \frac{c}{8} + B_{0.5}(\alpha + 1, \beta)A = \mu_1 \\ \frac{c}{24} + B_{0.5}(\alpha + 2, \beta)A = \mu_2 \\ \frac{c}{64} + B_{0.5}(\alpha + 3, \beta)A = \mu_3 \end{cases}$$

which can be solved numerically by the algorithm

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad \begin{bmatrix} C^{h+1} \\ A^{h+1} \\ \alpha^{h+1} \\ \beta^{h+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C^h \\ A^h \\ \alpha^h \\ \beta^h \end{bmatrix} - M^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \psi_1(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h) \\ \psi_2(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h) \\ \psi_3(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h) \\ \psi_4(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h) \end{bmatrix}$$

where the Jacobian matrix is given by

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad M = \begin{bmatrix} \left. \frac{\partial \psi_1}{\partial c} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_1}{\partial A} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_1}{\partial \alpha} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_1}{\partial \beta} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} \\ \left. \frac{\partial \psi_2}{\partial c} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_2}{\partial A} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_2}{\partial \alpha} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_2}{\partial \beta} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} \\ \left. \frac{\partial \psi_3}{\partial c} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_3}{\partial A} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_3}{\partial \alpha} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_3}{\partial \beta} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} \\ \left. \frac{\partial \psi_4}{\partial c} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_4}{\partial A} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_4}{\partial \alpha} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} & \left. \frac{\partial \psi_4}{\partial \beta} \right|_{(C^h, A^h, \alpha^h, \beta^h)} \end{bmatrix}$$

and with the derivatives given by

$$\text{Eq. 20} \quad \frac{\partial \psi_j}{\partial c} = \frac{1}{2^j}, \quad j = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

$$\text{Eq. 21} \quad \frac{\partial \psi_j}{\partial A} = B_{0.5}(\alpha + j - 1, \beta), \quad j = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

$$\text{Eq. 22} \quad \frac{\partial \psi_j}{\partial \alpha} = A \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \binom{\beta - 1}{k} \frac{(1/2)^{\alpha + j - 1 + k}}{k + \alpha + j - 1} \left(\ln \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{k + \alpha + j - 1} \right), \quad j = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

$$\text{Eq. 23} \quad \frac{\partial \psi_j}{\partial \beta} = A \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{(1/2)^{\alpha + j - 1 + k}}{(k + \alpha + j - 1)k!} \sum_{i=1}^k s(k, i) i (\beta - 1)^{i-1}, \quad j = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

with $s(k, i)$ indicating the Stirling numbers of the first kind. This method is discussed in detail [here](#) where it is also shown that it is not possible to identify the four unknowns such that the density in Eq. 11 closely matches the distribution in Figure 4, as it seems clear from Figure 5.

Figure 4. Distribution of minor allele frequency from zero to 0.5, with a detail for the interval $[0,0.1]$. The area of each box is equal to the number of variants whose minor allele frequency is included within the interval of the horizontal axis covered by its base.

Figure 5. We have here the same empirical distribution of Figure 4 compared with the density $f(\varphi)$ for $C = 10^7$ and various sets of values for α, β, A (see legend). I have found them by imposing $\varphi_M = 0.001$, $f(\varphi_M) = 1.1644 \cdot 10^9$, where φ_M is the frequency in which the distribution has its maximum, and increasing values for α .

4.5.1 Distributions for subsets of variants

If we consider only the non coding variants, we have the following distribution.

If we select only the 308,879 coding variants and then we select the three subsets (missense, ptv, synonymous) we have the following distributions.

4.6 Statistics

4.6.1 Bonferroni correction

If we accept a threshold α' for statistical significance and we perform m tests, then the probability that one test is positive by chance is $P < \alpha'$ and the probability that one test is negative by chance is $1 - P > 1 - \alpha'$. This means that the probability that all the m tests are negative by chance is $(1 - P)^m > (1 - \alpha')^m$. Therefore, the probability that at least one test is positive purely by chance is

$$\text{Eq. 24} \quad p = 1 - (1 - P)^m < 1 - (1 - \alpha')^m$$

We want this probability to be lower than α which leads to the conclusion

$$\text{Eq. 25} \quad \alpha' < 1 - (1 - \alpha)^{\frac{1}{m}}$$

By considering the well-known expansion by series $(1 - \alpha)^{\frac{1}{m}} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \binom{\frac{1}{m}}{k} (-\alpha)^k$ and by taking only the first two addends of the series we conclude with the condition:

$$\text{Eq. 26} \quad p < \frac{\alpha}{m}$$

This is the Bonferroni correction and usually, we assume $\alpha = 0.5$. The *correction* m is the number of independent tests.

4.6.2 Linkage disequilibrium

In genome sequencing, the number m of independent tests is given by the number of variants passed from one generation to the other in a completely independent fashion. While it is clear that variants on different chromosomes are independent, when we deal with *loci* on the same chromosome, in general variants belonging to the same chromosome are not inherited independently: we know that whole chunks of chromosomes of about 50 kb pass from one generation to the other. These blocks are called haplotypes and there has been a considerable effort in classifying them for various human populations in the last 20 years. A map of human haplotypes is now available (HapMap) and it allows for the calculation of the real number of independent variants (often called tag SNPs) on the human Genome, and for other pivotal purposes, like for instance *imputation* (a technique that dramatically reduces the number of variants we must genotype to scan the genome of a human being) (The International HapMap Consortium 2005), (The International HapMap Consortium, 2009). When two loci are on the same haplotype, they are said to be in linkage disequilibrium, while when they are transmitted independently, they are in linkage equilibrium. More precisely, let us consider two loci: L_1 can be occupied by allele A or a , L_2 can be occupied by allele B or b . We can define the two random variables:

$$\text{Eq. 27} \quad X_1 = \begin{cases} 0 \leftarrow L_1 = AA \\ 1 \leftarrow L_1 = aA \\ 2 \leftarrow L_1 = aa \end{cases}, \quad X_2 = \begin{cases} 0 \leftarrow L_2 = BB \\ 1 \leftarrow L_2 = bB \\ 2 \leftarrow L_2 = bb \end{cases}$$

That said, we define the linkage disequilibrium between the two loci as the second power of the correlation coefficient between X_1 and X_2 and we call it ρ^2 . In other words:

$$\text{Eq. 28} \quad \rho^2 = \varrho_{X_1 X_2}^2 = \left(\frac{\text{Cov}(X_1 X_2)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(X_1) \text{Var}(X_2)}} \right)^2$$

By introducing the frequencies of the four possible haplotypes AB, aa, Ab, aB we find⁵ the relations

$$\text{Eq. 29} \quad \begin{cases} f(Ab) = f(A) - f(AB) \\ f(aB) = f(B) - f(AB) \\ f(ab) = 1 - f(B) - f(A) + f(AB) \\ f(AB) + f(Ab) + f(aB) + f(ab) = 1 \\ f(A) + f(a) = f(B) + f(b) = 1 \end{cases}$$

and the linkage disequilibrium can be written also

$$\text{Eq. 30} \quad \rho^2 = \frac{a^2}{f(A)f(a)f(B)f(b)} = \frac{a^2}{(f(Ab)+f(AB))(1-f(Ab)-f(AB))(f(aB)+f(AB))(1-f(aB)-f(AB))}$$

with

⁵ For instance, we have $f(AB) = E[X_1 X_2]$ and $f(Ab) = E[X_1(1 - X_2)] = E[X_1] - E[X_1 X_2]$, where $E[X_1] = f(A)$, therefore we can write $f(Ab) = f(A) - f(AB)$. the other relations are deduced in a similar fashion.

$$\text{Eq. 31} \quad \begin{cases} d = f(AB) - f(A)f(B) = f(ab) - f(b)f(a) \\ d = f(A)f(b) - f(Ab) = f(a)f(B) - f(aB) \end{cases}$$

or also

$$\text{Eq. 32} \quad d = f(AB)f(ab) - f(Ab)f(aB)$$

We have that $\rho^2 \in [0,1]$, $d \in \left[-\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}\right]$ with the three extreme cases collected in the table below.

Linkage		Frequencies of Loci	d	ρ^2
equilibrium		$f(AB) = f(A)f(B)$	0	0
complete disequilibrium	coupling	$\begin{cases} f(AB) + f(ab) = 1 \\ f(aB) = f(Ab) = 0 \end{cases}$	$f(AB)f(ab)$	1
	repulsion	$\begin{cases} f(Ab) + f(aB) = 1 \\ f(ab) = f(AB) = 0 \end{cases}$	$-f(Ab)f(aB)$	1

Also useful are the relations that give the frequencies of the haplotypes from the frequencies of the alleles and the expressions of the alleles from the frequencies of the haplotypes:

$$\text{Eq. 33} \quad \begin{cases} f(AB) = d + f(A)f(B) \\ f(Ab) = f(A)f(b) - d \\ f(ab) = d + f(a)f(b) \\ f(aB) = f(a)f(B) - d \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} f(AB) = \rho\sqrt{f(A)f(a)f(B)f(b)} + f(A)f(B) \\ f(Ab) = f(A)f(b) - \rho\sqrt{f(A)f(a)f(B)f(b)} \\ f(ab) = \rho\sqrt{f(A)f(a)f(B)f(b)} + f(a)f(b) \\ f(aB) = f(a)f(B) - \rho\sqrt{f(A)f(a)f(B)f(b)} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Eq. 34} \quad \begin{cases} f(A) = f(Ab) + f(AB) \\ f(a) = 1 - f(A) \\ f(B) = f(aB) + f(AB) \\ f(b) = 1 - f(B) \end{cases}$$

These equations can be easily obtained from Eq. 29, Eq. 31. We can also write ρ in terms of conditional probabilities:

$$P(A|b) = \frac{f(Ab)}{f(b)} \Rightarrow f(Ab) = P(A|b)f(b), \quad P(A|B) = \frac{f(AB)}{f(B)} \Rightarrow f(AB) = P(A|B)f(B)$$

$$P(a|b) = \frac{f(ab)}{f(b)} \Rightarrow f(ab) = P(a|b)f(b), \quad P(a|B) = \frac{f(aB)}{f(B)} \Rightarrow f(aB) = P(a|B)f(B)$$

We then consider that

$$1 - P(A|b) = 1 - \frac{f(Ab)}{f(b)} = \frac{f(b) - f(Ab)}{f(b)} = \frac{f(ab)}{f(b)} = P(a|b)$$

$$1 - P(A|B) = 1 - \frac{f(AB)}{f(B)} = \frac{f(B) - f(AB)}{f(B)} = \frac{f(aB)}{f(B)} = P(a|B)$$

So we can conclude

$$\text{Eq. 35} \quad \begin{cases} f(Ab) = P(A|b)(1 - f(B)) \\ f(AB) = P(A|B)f(B) \\ f(ab) = P(a|b)(1 - f(B)) \\ f(aB) = P(a|B)f(B) \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} f(Ab) = P(A|b)(1 - f(B)) \\ f(AB) = P(A|B)f(B) \\ f(ab) = (1 - P(A|b))(1 - f(B)) \\ f(aB) = (1 - P(A|B))f(B) \end{cases}$$

By substituting the first and the second of these relationships into the first of Eq. 34 we get

$$\text{Eq. 36} \quad f(A) = P(A|b)(1 - f(B)) + P(A|B)f(B)$$

By substituting the first and the second of these relationships into the first of Eq. 33 we get

$$\rho = \frac{P(A|B) - f(A)}{\sqrt{f(A)f(a)f(B)f(b)}} f(B) = (P(A|B) - f(A)) \sqrt{\frac{f(B)}{f(A)f(a)f(b)}}$$

If we now put Eq. 36 into this expression, we have

$$\rho = (P(A|B) - P(A|b))(1 - f(B)) \sqrt{\frac{f(B)}{f(A)f(a)f(b)}} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 37} \quad \rho = (P(A|B) - P(A|b)) \sqrt{\frac{f(B)(1-f(B))}{f(A)(1-f(A))}}$$

Also, from Eq. 33 we have

$$d = f(AB) - f(A)f(B) \Rightarrow \begin{cases} d \leq f(A) - f(A)f(B) \\ d \leq f(B) - f(A)f(B) \end{cases} = \begin{cases} d \leq f(A)f(b) \\ d \leq f(a)f(B) \end{cases}$$

$$d = f(ab) - f(b)f(a) \Rightarrow \begin{cases} d \leq f(a) - f(a)f(b) \\ d \leq f(b) - f(a)f(b) \end{cases} = \begin{cases} d \leq f(a)f(B) \\ d \leq f(A)f(b) \end{cases}$$

$$d = f(A)f(b) - f(Ab) \Rightarrow \begin{cases} d \geq f(A)f(b) - f(A) \\ d \geq f(A)f(b) - f(b) \end{cases} = \begin{cases} d \geq -f(A)f(B) \\ d \geq -f(a)f(b) \end{cases}$$

$$d = f(a)f(B) - f(aB) \Rightarrow \begin{cases} d \geq f(a)f(B) - f(a) \\ d \geq f(a)f(B) - f(B) \end{cases} = \begin{cases} d \geq -f(a)f(b) \\ d \geq -f(A)f(B) \end{cases}$$

By removing the redundant inequalities we have

$$\text{Eq. 38} \quad \begin{cases} d \leq f(A)f(b) \\ d \leq f(a)f(B) \\ d \geq -f(a)f(b) \\ d \geq -f(A)f(B) \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \rho \leq \sqrt{\frac{f(A)f(b)}{f(a)f(B)}} \\ \rho \leq \sqrt{\frac{f(a)f(B)}{f(A)f(b)}} \\ \rho \geq -\sqrt{\frac{f(a)f(b)}{f(A)f(B)}} \\ \rho \geq -\sqrt{\frac{f(A)f(B)}{f(a)f(b)}} \end{cases}$$

For $f(a) \leq f(A), f(b) \leq f(B)$ and assuming that $f(a) \leq f(b)$ (which means $f(A) \geq f(B)$) we have $f(a)f(B) \leq f(A)f(b)$ and $-f(a)f(b) \geq -f(A)f(B)$, hence we remain with the inequalities

$$\text{Eq. 39} \quad -f(a)f(b) \leq d \leq f(B)f(a) \Leftrightarrow -\sqrt{\frac{f(a)f(b)}{f(A)f(B)}} \leq \rho \leq \sqrt{\frac{f(B)f(a)}{f(b)f(A)}}$$

If we set $f(b) = y$ and $f(a) = xy$, we have

$$\text{Eq. 40} \quad -xy^2 \leq d \leq (1-y)xy \Leftrightarrow -\sqrt{\frac{xy^2}{(1-xy)(1-y)}} \leq \rho \leq \sqrt{\frac{(1-y)x}{1-xy}}, \quad \begin{cases} x \in [0,1] \\ y \in [0, \frac{1}{2}] \end{cases}$$

Figure 6. Range of variability of ρ (left) and of d (right).

If we plot the surfaces that limit d and ρ (Figure 6) we recognize that for LD to be high in absolute value, $f(a)$ must be close to $f(b)$ and high negative LD can be obtained only when the condition $f(b) \sim 0.5$ is fulfilled too.

4.6.3 Number of independent loci and false discovery rate

From an operational point of view, how can we determine if two loci are in linkage equilibrium so that they can be considered independent one from the other? We can randomly build the genome of thousands of human beings with the only restraint that haplotypes must be respected (this is where the HapMap comes into play), we then randomly assign them to two populations and we calculate for each locus the p value for the comparison of these two populations. Let's say that locus L_i has a p value p_i . Since these two groups are identical by construction, it must be $p > \alpha/m$ or, in other words, $m > \alpha/p_i$. If we repeat this inequality for each locus, we have a lower bound for m . That number is the number of independent loci we were searching for. One such experiment led to a value $m = 1.1 \cdot 10^6$ for whole-genome variants with a minor allele frequency of more than 0.05, in the European population (Pe'er, I. et al. 2008), which means a cut-off $p < 4,54 \cdot 10^{-8}$ for statistical significance in studies involving that kind of variants.

More recently, a similar study calculated a value $m = 782361$ in whole-genome sequencing data, in the European population, for variants with a minor allele frequency of more than 0.05. This value has been calculated by assuming that two loci are independent when $\rho^2 < 0.8$. By applying these same parameters to data from whole-exome sequencing, the same research group calculated several independent loci $m = 39383$. By substituting these two values in α/m , with $\alpha = 0.05$, we obtain the cut-off for significance of $6.39 \cdot 10^{-8}$ and $1.27 \cdot 10^{-6}$, respectively (see Table 36) (Fadista, J. et al. 2016).

Sequencing	m	p	LD cut-off	MAF	Population
WGS	782361	$6.39 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$\rho^2 < 0.8$	> 0.05	European
WES	39383	$1.27 \cdot 10^{-6}$			

Table 36. Number of independent loci among Europeans, for common variants. WGS: whole-genome sequencing; WES: whole-exome sequencing; MAF: minor allele frequency. From (Fadista, J. et al. 2016).

In another set of simulations and analyses of previously published associations between traits and variants, it has been shown that if we switch from $\alpha' = 5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ to $\alpha' = 5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ in studies including about $130 \cdot 10^3$ individuals, then we have an increase of 93% in true positive associations with an empirical false discovery rate ($eFDR$) which increases by 2.2%, where $eFDR = V/R$, with V being the number of false-positive associations and the R the total number of associated loci (Chen Z. et al 2021).

4.6.4 Cut-off for statistical significance

We are here dealing with European subjects, variants with $MAF > 0.05$, and sample size $n > 130 \cdot 10^3$, so it seems legit to take into account both Table 36 and the relaxed cut-off suggested in (Chen Z. et al 2021). Hence, I apply the widely recognized cut-off of $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ for statistical significance to all the variants, and then I define a suggestive cut-off of $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$.

4.6.5 Calculating a p value for each variant

For each variant genotyped we can build a table like the following one, where S_0 is the number of individuals who have the disease ($Y = 1$) and who have two reference alleles ($X = 0$), S_1 is the number of individuals who have the disease and have one reference allele and one alternative allele, and so on. In other words, for each subject, the dependent variable Y indicates the disease status, while the explanatory variable X indicates the genotype.

	$X = 0$	$X = 1$	$X = 2$	
$Y = 1$	S_0	S_1	S_2	n_D
$Y = 0$	R_0	R_1	R_2	n_H

This also means that if n_D is the number of subjects with the disease and n_H is the size of the control group, then we can write

$$S_0 + S_1 + S_2 = n_D, \quad R_0 + R_1 + R_2 = n_H$$

Moreover, if $f_D(A)$ is the frequency of reference allele among patients, while $f_H(A)$ is the frequency of the same allele among healthy subjects, we can write

$$f_D(A) = \frac{2S_0 + S_1}{2(S_0 + S_1 + S_2)}, \quad f_D(a) = \frac{2S_2 + S_1}{2(S_0 + S_1 + S_2)}$$

$$f_H(A) = \frac{2R_0 + R_1}{2(R_0 + R_1 + R_2)}, \quad f_H(a) = \frac{2R_2 + R_1}{2(R_0 + R_1 + R_2)}$$

where a is the alternative allele. By combining these equations we get the linear system

$$\text{Eq. 41} \quad \begin{cases} 2S_0 + S_1 = 2n_D f_D(A) \\ 2S_2 + S_1 = 2n_D f_D(a) \\ 2R_0 + R_1 = 2n_H f_H(A) \\ 2R_2 + R_1 = 2n_H f_H(a) \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} S_0 = n_D f_D(A) - n_D f_D(a) + S_2 \\ S_1 = 2n_D f_D(a) - 2S_2 \\ R_0 = n_H f_H(A) - n_H f_H(a) + R_2 \\ R_1 = 2n_H f_H(a) - 2R_2 \end{cases}$$

4.6.5.1 Logistic regression

All that said, the relationship between the independent variable and the explanatory one in GWAS studies is set as

$$\text{Eq. 42} \quad \log \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X=x)}{P(Y=0|X=x)} \right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x, \quad x = 0, 1, 2$$

For $x = 0$ this model gives

$$\text{Eq. 43} \quad \beta_0 = \log \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=0)} \right) = \log \left(\frac{S_0}{R_0} \right)$$

Thus, for $x = 1$ we get

$$\text{Eq. 44} \quad \beta_1 = \log \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X=1)}{P(Y=0|X=1)} / \frac{P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=0)} \right) = \log \left(\frac{S_1 R_0}{R_1 S_0} \right)$$

In other words, β_1 is the logarithm of the ratio between the odds of having the disease with genotype $X = 1$ and the odds of having the disease with genotype $X = 0$. For $x = 2$ we can also write

$$\log \left(\frac{P(Y = 1|X = 2)}{P(Y = 0|X = 2)} \right) = \beta_0 + 2\beta_1 =$$

$$= \log \left(\frac{P(Y = 1|X = 0)}{P(Y = 0|X = 0)} \right) + \log \left(\frac{P(Y = 1|X = 1)/P(Y = 1|X = 0)}{P(Y = 0|X = 1)/P(Y = 0|X = 0)} \right)^2 \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 45} \quad OR_{2,0} = \frac{P(Y=1|X=2)/P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=2)/P(Y=0|X=0)} = \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X=1)/P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=1)/P(Y=0|X=0)} \right)^2 = OR_{1,0}^2$$

So the odds ratio relative to the genotype $X = 2$ is the second power of the odds ratio for the genotype $X = 1$. From this equation we also find $\frac{S_2 R_0}{R_2 S_0} = \left(\frac{S_1 R_0}{S_0 R_1} \right)^2$ which can be simplified into:

$$\text{Eq. 46} \quad \frac{S_2}{R_2} = \frac{R_0 S_1^2}{S_0 R_1^2}$$

By applying the Bayesian formula we have

$$\begin{aligned} P(Y = 1|X = 1) &= \frac{P(Y = 1)P(X = 1|Y = 1)}{P(X = 1)} & P(Y = 1|X = 0) &= \frac{P(Y = 1)P(X = 0|Y = 1)}{P(X = 0)} \\ P(Y = 0|X = 1) &= \frac{P(Y = 0)P(X = 1|Y = 0)}{P(X = 1)} & P(Y = 0|X = 0) &= \frac{P(Y = 0)P(X = 0|Y = 0)}{P(X = 0)} \end{aligned}$$

which leads to an alternative expression for the odds ratio relative to the genotype $X = 1$:

$$\text{Eq. 47} \quad OR_{1,0} = \frac{P(Y=1|X=1)/P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=1)/P(Y=0|X=0)} = \frac{P(X=1|Y=1)/P(X=0|Y=1)}{P(X=1|Y=0)/P(X=0|Y=0)}$$

Analogously we have

$$\text{Eq. 48} \quad OR_{2,0} = \frac{P(Y=1|X=2)/P(Y=1|X=0)}{P(Y=0|X=2)/P(Y=0|X=0)} = \frac{P(X=2|Y=1)/P(X=0|Y=1)}{P(X=2|Y=0)/P(X=0|Y=0)}$$

By using this expression we can derive some other relationships:

$$f_D(aA) = P(X = 1|Y = 1) = OR_{1,0} \frac{P(X = 0|Y = 1)P(X = 1|Y = 0)}{P(X = 0|Y = 0)}$$

$$f_D(aa) = P(X = 2|Y = 1) = OR_{2,0} \frac{P(X = 0|Y = 1)P(X = 2|Y = 0)}{P(X = 0|Y = 0)}$$

We can then find $f_D(AA) = 1 - f_D(aa) - f_D(aA)$. In conclusion, we have

$$\text{Eq. 49} \quad \begin{cases} f_D(aA) = OR_{1,0} \frac{f_D(AA)f_H(aA)}{f_H(AA)} \\ f_D(aa) = OR_{2,0} \frac{f_D(AA)f_H(aa)}{f_H(AA)} \\ f_D(AA) = \left(1 + OR_{1,0} \frac{f_H(aA)}{f_H(AA)} + OR_{2,0} \frac{f_H(aa)}{f_H(AA)} \right)^{-1} \end{cases}$$

The null hypothesis is assumed to be the equality between the odds of having the disease under genotypes $X = 1$ and $X = 0$:

$$\text{Eq. 50} \quad H_0: \frac{\frac{p_1}{1-p_1}}{\frac{p_0}{1-p_0}} = 1 \Leftrightarrow p_1 = p_0 \Leftrightarrow \beta_1 = 0$$

Figure 7. The continuous line is the density of $\beta_1 = \log(OR)$ under the null hypothesis, for $n = 50, p = 0.8$. On the left I have used Eq. 52 (in this case the density of p is approximated by a beta law), on the right I have used Eq. 51 (in this case the density of p is approximated by a normal law). The dashed line is the density of the law $N(0, \text{Var}(\log(OR)))$, with $\text{Var}(\log(OR)) \cong \frac{4}{np(1-p)}$.

It can be shown that under this hypothesis the random variable $L = \log\left(\frac{\frac{p_1}{1-p_1}}{\frac{p_0}{1-p_0}}\right)$ has a density that is given by the following two expressions:

$$\text{Eq. 51} \quad f_L(t) = \frac{ne^t}{4\pi p(1-p)} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\frac{n}{4p(1-p)}\left(\left(\frac{x}{x+1}-p\right)^2 + \left(\frac{x}{x+e^t}-p\right)^2\right)} \frac{dx}{(x+1)^2(x+e^t)^2}, \quad t \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$\text{Eq. 52} \quad f_L(t) = \frac{e^{t\beta}}{B^2(\alpha, \beta)} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{x^{2\alpha-1}}{(x+1)^{\frac{n}{2}-1}(x+e^t)^{\frac{n}{2}-1}} dx, \quad t \in \mathbb{R}, \begin{cases} \alpha = p\left(\frac{n}{2}-1\right) \\ \beta = (1-p)\left(\frac{n}{2}-1\right) \end{cases}$$

where $p = p_0 = p_1$ and n is the size of the total sample (diseased plus healthy). It is also possible to show that an approximated expression for the expectation and the variance of these densities is

$$\text{Eq. 53} \quad E[L] \cong 0, \quad \text{Var}(L) \cong \frac{4}{np(1-p)}$$

A detailed derivation of the last formulae can be found in (Maccallini P. 2022). A remarkable observation is that these densities approximate the law $N(0, \text{Var}(L))$, see Figure 7 for an example. But this also means that under H_0 we have approximately

$$\text{Eq. 54} \quad \frac{L}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(\log(OR))}} \sim N(0,1)$$

Moreover, we can write

$$\text{Var}(L) \cong \frac{4}{np(1-p)} = \frac{2}{np(1-p)} + \frac{2}{np(1-p)} \cong$$

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$$\cong \frac{1}{S_0 \left(1 - \frac{S_0}{S_0+R_0}\right)} + \frac{1}{S_1 \left(1 - \frac{S_1}{S_1+R_1}\right)} = \frac{S_0 + R_0}{S_0 R_0} + \frac{S_1 + R_1}{S_1 R_1} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 55} \quad \text{Var}(L) \cong \frac{1}{R_0} + \frac{1}{S_0} + \frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{S_1}$$

All that said, we can test the hypothesis by using the density in Eq. 54 and say that the null hypothesis is rejected when

$$2P\left(z < -\frac{|\log(OR)|}{\sqrt{\text{Var}[\log(OR)]}}\right) = 2\Phi\left(-\frac{|\log(OR)|}{\sqrt{\text{Var}[\log(OR)]}}\right) < p \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 56} \quad 2\Phi\left(-\frac{|\beta_1|}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{R_0} + \frac{1}{S_0} + \frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{S_1}}}\right) < p$$

where $p = 5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ is the corrected p value discussed in par. 4.6.4. As an example, for variant 13:41353297:G:A, females only, phenotype 20002_1482 we have

$$\begin{aligned} n_D &= 1208 & f_D(A) &= 0.447848 & \beta_1 &= -1.40 \cdot 10^{-3} \\ n_H &= 192945 & f_H(A) &= 0.505688 & SEM &= 2.52 \cdot 10^{-4} \end{aligned}$$

where $SEM = \sqrt{\frac{1}{R_0} + \frac{1}{S_0} + \frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{S_1}}$. Then for the testing of the null hypothesis we have

$$2\left(1 - \Phi\left(\frac{|\beta_1|}{SEM}\right)\right) = 2(1 - \Phi(5.55)) = 2 \cdot 10^{-8}$$

By combining Eq. 41 and the following equations

$$\text{Eq. 57} \quad \begin{cases} \frac{S_1 R_0}{S_0 R_1} = e^{\beta_1} \\ \left(\frac{S_1 R_0}{S_0 R_1}\right)^2 = \frac{S_2 R_0}{S_0 R_2} \end{cases}$$

we have a non-linear system in 6 equations and six unknowns $S_0, S_1, S_2, R_0, R_1, R_2$ whose solution is

Eq. 58

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} S_0 = \frac{f_D(A)(e^\beta - 2(e^\beta - 1)f_H(A)) - f_H(A)}{(e^\beta - 1)((e^\beta - 1)f_H(A) - e^\beta)} n_D \\ S_1 = 2 \frac{f_D(A)((e^{2\beta} - 1)f_H(A) - e^{2\beta}) + f_H(A)}{(e^\beta - 1)((e^\beta - 1)f_H(A) - e^\beta)} n_D \\ S_2 = \frac{(e^\beta - 2)f_H(A) - e^\beta + 1 - f_D(A)(2(e^\beta - 1)f_H(A) - 2e^\beta + 1)}{(e^\beta - 1)((e^\beta - 1)f_H(A) - e^\beta)} e^\beta n_D \\ R_0 = \frac{f_H(A) + f_D(A)(2(e^\beta - 1)f_H(A) - e^\beta)}{(e^\beta - 1)((e^\beta - 1)f_D(A) + 1)} e^\beta n_H \\ R_1 = -2 \frac{f_D(A)((e^{2\beta} - 1)f_H(A) - e^{2\beta}) + f_H(A)}{(e^\beta - 1)((e^\beta - 1)f_D(A) + 1)} n_H \\ R_2 = \frac{e^\beta - 1 - (e^\beta - 2)f_H(A) + f_D(A)(2(e^\beta - 1)f_H(A) - 2e^\beta + 1)}{(e^\beta - 1)((e^\beta - 1)f_D(A) + 1)} n_H \end{array} \right.$$

to derive the following table:

	$X = 0$	$X = 1$	$X = 2$
$Y = 1$	$S_0 = 371$	$S_1 = 340$	$S_2 = 497$
$Y = 0$	$R_0 = 71072$	$R_1 = 52996$	$R_2 = 68877$

Note that if you try to find the analytical solution of Eq. 41, Eq. 57 you get very complex expressions (I have tried with Mathematica). I solved it numerically instead (Newton-Raphson method). Note that we use Eq. 46 we have

$$\frac{S_2}{R_2} = \frac{R_0 S_1^2}{S_0 R_1^2} = 7.885 \cdot 10^{-3}$$

while with the numbers collected in the table we have $\frac{S_2}{R_2} = 7.216 \cdot 10^{-3}$. Hence, the hypothesis stated in Eq. 45 is almost correct, in this case.

4.6.6 Testing Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium

Deviation from the Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium is considered to be an indication of genotyping error. Let us consider the experimental data in the following table, which refers to a particular variant.

genotype	AA	Aa	aa
number of individuals	n_0	n_1	n_2

We have that the frequencies of the two alleles are given by:

$$f(A) = \frac{2n_0 + n_1}{2(n_0 + n_1 + n_2)}, \quad f(a) = \frac{n_1 + 2n_2}{2(n_0 + n_1 + n_2)}$$

If the Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium holds (null hypothesis) we have

$$H_0: n_0 = Nf^2(A), \quad n_1 = 2Nf(A)f(a), \quad n_2 = Nf^2(a)$$

Figure 8. The density of T for $f(A) = 0.2$ and increasing values of N (left) and for $N = 200$ and increasing values of $f(A)$ (right). The density $\chi^2(1)$ is also reported (dashed line), for a comparison.

According to the central limit theorem, the value $f(A)$ can be described by the normal random variable

$$X \sim N\left(f(A), \frac{f(A)(1-f(A))}{2N}\right)$$

where $N = n_0 + n_1 + n_2$. If we now consider the random variable

$$\begin{cases} T = \frac{(h_0 - NX^2)^2}{h_0} + \frac{(h_1 - 2NX(1-X))^2}{h_1} + \frac{(h_2 - N(1-X)^2)^2}{h_2} \\ h_0 = Nf^2(A), \quad h_1 = 2Nf(A)f(a), \quad h_2 = Nf^2(a) \end{cases}$$

what is its density? It can be proved that it approximates a law $\chi^2(1)$ (Chi-square law with one degree of freedom). And if we use a normal random generator for X and we plot the empirical density of T for different values of $N, f(A)$ we can see how it closely matches the density $\chi^2(1)$ (Figure 8). This suggests that we can test the null hypothesis (Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium) by calculating the probability $P(T > t)$ where

$$\begin{cases} t = \frac{(h_0 - n_0)^2}{h_0} + \frac{(h_1 - n_1)^2}{h_1} + \frac{(h_2 - n_2)^2}{h_2} \\ h_0 = Nf^2(A), \quad h_1 = 2Nf(A)f(a), \quad h_2 = Nf^2(a) \end{cases}$$

with $T \sim \chi^2(1)$. In GWAS, a p value below 10^{-6} is assumed to be an indication of a violation of the HWE and thus it is considered a flag for genotyping error. As an example, if we consider variant 1:693731:A:G from variants.tsv we have the following table.

genotype	<i>AA</i>	<i>AG</i>	<i>GG</i>
number of individuals	$n_0 = 281659$	$n_1 = 74692$	$n_2 = 4841$

Thus, we have $f(A) = \frac{2n_0+n_1}{2(n_0+n_1+n_2)} = 0.8832$ and value t is the following one:

$$t = \frac{(n_0 - Nf^2(A))^2}{Nf^2(A)} + \frac{(n_1 - 2Nf(A)(1 - f(A)))^2}{2Nf(A)f(a)} + \frac{(n_2 - N(1 - f(A))^2)^2}{Nf^2(a)} = 1.9429$$

We calculate $P(T > t) = 0.1634$. The calculation is performed by the following script.

4.6.6.1 Script

```
% file name = HWE_testing
% date of creation = 26/04/2022
pkg load statistics
clear all
close all
%-----
% Experimental Data
%-----
n0 = 281659; % observed
n1 = 74692; % observed
n2 = 4841; % observed
N = n0 + n1 + n2;
%-----
% Derived parameters
%-----
fA = 0.5*( 2*n0 + n1 )/N;
h0 = N*fA^2; % individuals AA expected under H0
h1 = 2*N*fA*(1-fA); % individuals Aa expected under H0
h2 = N*(1-fA)^2; % individuals aa expected under H0
t1 = ( ( h0 - n0 )^2 )/h0;
t2 = ( ( h1 - n1 )^2 )/h1;
t3 = ( ( h2 - n2 )^2 )/h2;
t = t1 + t2 + t3
%-----
% Hypothesis testing
%-----
p_value = 1 - chi2cdf(t,1)
```

4.7 Effect of Linkage Disequilibrium on regression analysis

Let us consider two loci L_1, L_2 : the former can be occupied by allele A or a , and the latter can be occupied by allele B or b . We can define the two random variables:

$$\text{Eq. 59} \quad X_1 = \begin{cases} 0 \leftarrow L_1 = AA \\ 1 \leftarrow L_1 = aA \\ 2 \leftarrow L_1 = aa \end{cases}, \quad X_2 = \begin{cases} 0 \leftarrow L_2 = BB \\ 1 \leftarrow L_2 = bB \\ 2 \leftarrow L_2 = bb \end{cases}$$

In other words, X_i is the number of alternative alleles in L_i , $i = 1, 2$. We assume that allele a gives a predisposition to the disease. We also assume that b is positively correlated with a . The presence of the disease is indicated by the binary variable Y . We then define the odds ratios at the two loci:

$$\text{Eq. 60} \quad OR_i \triangleq \frac{P(Y=1|X_i=1)/P(Y=0|X_i=1)}{P(Y=1|X_i=0)/P(Y=0|X_i=0)} = \frac{P(Y=1|X_i=1)/P(Y=0|X_i=1)}{P(Y=1|X_i=0)/P(Y=0|X_i=0)} \quad i = 1, 2$$

We can use the law of total probabilities and write

$$P(Y = 1|X_2 = 2) = P(Y = 1|X_1 = 0)P(AA|bb) + P(Y = 1|X_1 = 1)P(Aa|bb) + P(Y = 1|X_1 = 2)P(aa|bb)$$

$$P(Y = 1|X_2 = 0) = P(Y = 1|X_1 = 0)P(AA|BB) + P(Y = 1|X_1 = 1)P(Aa|BB) + P(Y = 1|X_1 = 2)P(aa|BB)$$

The ratio between these two equations gives

$$\frac{P(Y = 1|X_2 = 2)}{P(Y = 1|X_2 = 0)} = \frac{P(AA|bb) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(Aa|bb) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=2)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(aa|bb)}{P(AA|BB) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(Aa|BB) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=2)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(aa|BB)}$$

where we have also divided the numerator and the denominator of the second hand by $P(Y = 1|X_1 = 0)$. We now make the assumption that

$$\text{Eq. 61} \quad \frac{P(Y=1|X_i=2)}{P(Y=1|X_i=0)} = \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X_i=1)}{P(Y=1|X_i=0)} \right)^2 \quad i = 1, 2$$

This means that we assume that the relative risk of having the disease with two minor alleles is the second power of the relative risk of having the disease with only one minor allele. Remember that the minor allele at L_1 is the causal one (it predisposes to the disease) and the minor allele at L_2 is positively correlated with it. So the assumption is assumed to be true at both loci. Note now that

$$P(AA|bb) = P(A|b)^2, \quad P(Aa|bb) = 2P(A|b)P(a|b), \quad P(aa|bb) = P(a|b)^2$$

$$P(AA|BB) = P(A|B)^2, \quad P(Aa|BB) = 2P(A|B)P(a|B), \quad P(aa|BB) = P(a|B)^2$$

Therefore we find a significant simplification of the expression above:

$$\left(\frac{P(Y = 1|X_2 = 1)}{P(Y = 1|X_2 = 0)} \right)^2 = \frac{P(A|b)^2 + 2 \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(A|b)P(a|b) + \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)} \right)^2 P(a|b)^2}{P(A|B)^2 + 2 \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(A|B)P(a|B) + \left(\frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)} \right)^2 P(a|B)^2} =$$

$$= \frac{\left(P(A|b) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(a|b) \right)^2}{\left(P(A|B) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(a|B) \right)^2} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 62} \quad \frac{P(Y=1|X_2=1)}{P(Y=1|X_2=0)} = \frac{P(A|b) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(a|b)}{P(A|B) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(a|B)}$$

Equivalently, we have

$$\text{Eq. 63} \quad \frac{P(Y=1|X_2=1)}{P(Y=1|X_2=0)} - 1 = \frac{(P(A|b) - P(A|B)) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}(P(a|b) - P(a|B))}{P(A|B) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(a|B)}$$

By using again the law of total probabilities we write

$$P(Y = 0|X_2 = 2) = P(Y = 0|X_1 = 0)P(AA|bb) + P(Y = 0|X_1 = 1)P(Aa|bb) + P(Y = 0|X_1 = 2)P(aa|bb)$$

$$P(Y = 0|X_2 = 0) = P(Y = 0|X_1 = 0)P(AA|BB) + P(Y = 0|X_1 = 1)P(Aa|BB) + P(Y = 0|X_1 = 2)P(aa|BB)$$

By dividing each hand of the first equation by the corresponding member of the second one we have

$$\frac{P(Y = 0|X_2 = 2)}{P(Y = 0|X_2 = 0)} = \frac{P(AA|bb) + \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(Aa|bb) + \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=2)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(aa|bb)}{P(AA|BB) + \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(Aa|BB) + \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=2)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(aa|BB)}$$

We can then make the assumption

$$\text{Eq. 64} \quad \frac{P(Y=0|X_i=2)}{P(Y=0|X_i=0)} = \left(\frac{P(Y=0|X_i=1)}{P(Y=0|X_i=0)} \right)^2 \quad i = 1, 2$$

which again is based on the fact that the minor allele of the locus L_1 is a predisposing factor to the disease and the minor allele of L_2 is positively correlated with it. Therefore, we write

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{P(Y = 0|X_2 = 1)}{P(Y = 0|X_2 = 0)} \right)^2 &= \frac{P(AA|bb) + \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(Aa|bb) + \left(\frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)} \right)^2 P(aa|bb)}{P(AA|BB) + \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(Aa|BB) + \left(\frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)} \right)^2 P(aa|BB)} = \\ &= \frac{P(A|b)^2 + 2 \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(A|b)P(a|b) + \left(\frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)} \right)^2 P(a|b)^2}{P(A|B)^2 + 2 \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(A|B)P(a|B) + \left(\frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)} \right)^2 P(a|B)^2} \Rightarrow \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Eq. 65} \quad \frac{P(Y=0|X_2=1)}{P(Y=0|X_2=0)} = \frac{P(A|b) + \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(a|b)}{P(A|B) + \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(a|B)}$$

From Eq. 62 and Eq. 65 we derive the

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{P(Y = 1|X_2 = 1)}{P(Y = 1|X_2 = 0)} \bigg/ \frac{P(Y = 0|X_2 = 1)}{P(Y = 0|X_2 = 0)} = \\ &= \frac{P(A|b) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(a|b)}{P(A|B) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)}P(a|B)} \cdot \frac{P(A|B) + \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(a|B)}{P(A|b) + \frac{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}P(a|b)} = \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\frac{P(A|B)P(A|b)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)} + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)} P(A|B)P(a|b) + P(A|b)P(a|B) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)} P(a|b)P(a|B)}{\frac{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)} + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}} \\
= & \frac{\frac{P(A|B)P(A|b)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)} + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)} P(A|b)P(a|B) + P(A|B)P(a|b) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)} P(a|b)P(a|B)}{\frac{P(Y=0|X_1=0)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)} + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)}}
\end{aligned}$$

By considering the definitions in Eq. 60 we can write

$$\text{Eq. 66} \quad OR_2 = \frac{\frac{P(A|B)P(A|b)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)} + OR_1 P(A|B)P(a|b) + P(A|b)P(a|B) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)} P(a|b)P(a|B)}{\frac{P(A|B)P(A|b)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)} + OR_1 P(A|b)P(a|B) + P(A|B)P(a|b) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)} P(a|b)P(a|B)}$$

More conveniently we can write

$$\text{Eq. 67} \quad OR_2 - 1 = \frac{OR_1 (P(A|B)P(a|b) - P(A|b)P(a|B)) - (P(A|B)P(a|b) - P(A|b)P(a|B))}{\frac{P(A|B)P(A|b)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)} + OR_1 P(A|b)P(a|B) + P(A|B)P(a|b) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)} P(a|b)P(a|B)} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 67} \quad OR_2 - 1 = \frac{(OR_1 - 1)(P(A|B)P(a|b) - P(A|b)P(a|B))}{\frac{P(A|B)P(A|b)}{P(Y=0|X_1=1)} + OR_1 P(A|b)P(a|B) + P(A|B)P(a|b) + \frac{P(Y=1|X_1=1)}{P(Y=1|X_1=0)} P(a|b)P(a|B)}$$

If we now consider the contingency table below, we can write

$$\begin{cases} P(Y = 0|X_1 = 1) = \frac{R_1}{R_1 + S_1} \\ P(Y = 0|X_1 = 0) = \frac{R_0}{R_0 + S_0} \end{cases} \Rightarrow \frac{P(Y = 0|X_1 = 1)}{P(Y = 0|X_1 = 0)} = \frac{R_0 R_1 + S_0 R_1}{R_0 R_1 + R_0 S_1} = \frac{R_0 + S_0}{R_0 + OR_1 S_0} = \frac{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + 1}{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + OR_1}$$

$$\begin{cases} P(Y = 1|X_1 = 1) = \frac{S_1}{R_1 + S_1} \\ P(Y = 1|X_1 = 0) = \frac{S_0}{R_0 + S_0} \end{cases} \Rightarrow \frac{P(Y = 1|X_1 = 1)}{P(Y = 1|X_1 = 0)} = \frac{R_0 S_1 + S_0 S_1}{S_0 R_1 + S_0 S_1} = \frac{R_0 + S_0}{OR_1 + S_0} = \frac{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + 1}{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + OR_1} OR_1$$

	$X_1 = 0$	$X_1 = 1$	$X_1 = 2$	
$Y = 1$	S_0	S_1	S_2	n_D
$Y = 0$	R_0	R_1	R_2	n_H

Table 37. Contingency table for locus L_1 .

Where we have considered that

$$\text{Eq. 68} \quad OR_1 = \frac{S_1 R_0}{S_0 R_1}$$

Then the denominator of Eq. 67 can be written

$$\begin{aligned}
DEN &= \frac{P(A|B)P(A|b)}{\frac{\frac{R_0+1}{S_0}}{\frac{R_0+OR_1}{S_0}}} + OR_1 P(A|b)P(a|B) + P(A|B)P(a|b) + \frac{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + 1}{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + OR_1} OR_1 P(a|b)P(a|B) = \\
&= P(A|B) \left(\frac{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + OR_1}{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + 1} P(A|b) + P(a|b) \right) + OR_1 P(a|B) \left(P(A|b) + \frac{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + 1}{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + OR_1} P(a|b) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Then we find the expression

$$\text{Eq. 69} \quad OR_2 - 1 = \frac{(OR_1 - 1)(P(A|B)P(a|b) - P(A|b)P(a|B))}{P(A|B) \left(\frac{\frac{R_0+OR_1}{S_0}}{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + 1} P(A|b) + P(a|b) \right) + OR_1 P(a|B) \left(P(A|b) + \frac{\frac{R_0+1}{S_0}}{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + OR_1} P(a|b) \right)}$$

From Eq. 33, and Eq. 34 we find

$$\text{Eq. 70} \quad \begin{cases} P(A|b) = \frac{f(A)f(b)-d}{f(b)} \\ P(A|B) = \frac{d+f(A)f(B)}{f(B)} \\ P(a|b) = \frac{d+f(a)f(b)}{f(b)} \\ P(a|B) = \frac{f(a)f(B)-d}{f(B)} \\ \frac{d}{f(b)f(B)} = P(A|B)P(a|b) - P(A|b)P(a|B) \end{cases}$$

By substituting Eq. 70 in Eq. 69 we get the expression of OR_2 as a function of OR_1 , d , and the frequencies of the alleles of both loci. For the nominator we have:

$$NUM = (OR_1 - 1)(P(A|B)P(a|b) - P(A|b)P(a|B)) = \frac{(OR_1 - 1)d}{f(b)f(B)}$$

For the denominator, we write

$$\begin{aligned}
DEN &= \frac{d + f(A)f(B)}{f(B)} \left(\frac{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + OR_1}{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + 1} \frac{f(A)f(b) - d}{f(b)} + \frac{d + f(a)f(b)}{f(b)} \right) + \\
&+ OR_1 \frac{f(a)f(B) - d}{f(B)} \left(\frac{f(A)f(b) - d}{f(b)} + \frac{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + 1}{\frac{R_0}{S_0} + OR_1} \frac{d + f(a)f(b)}{f(b)} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

In conclusion, we have

$$\text{Eq. 71} \quad OR_2 - 1 = \frac{(OR_1 - 1)d}{(d + f(A)f(B))(\theta(f(A)f(b) - d) + d + f(a)f(b)) + OR_1(f(a)f(B) - d)(f(A)f(b) - d + \frac{d + f(a)f(b)}{\theta})}$$

with $\theta = \left(\frac{R_0}{S_0} + OR_1\right) / \left(\frac{R_0}{S_0} + 1\right)$. For values of OR_1 that tend to be close to 1 (in our case $OR_1 > 1$), it might be possible to make the approximation

$$\text{Eq. 72} \quad \frac{\frac{R_0 + OR_1}{S_0}}{\frac{R_0 + 1}{S_0}} \sim \frac{\frac{R_0 + 1}{S_0}}{\frac{R_0 + OR_1}{S_0}} \sim 1$$

Then we have

$$\text{Eq. 73} \quad OR_2 - 1 = \frac{(OR_1 - 1)d}{[d + f(A)f(B) + OR_1(f(a)f(B) - d)]f(b)} = \frac{(OR_1 - 1)d}{f(b)[f(B) + (OR_1 - 1)(f(a)f(B) - d)]}$$

which is the same as Eq. 3 of (Zondervan KT, Cardon LR 2004) once we switch minor alleles with major ones.

4.7.1 An approximated formula

In GWAS studies, the regression model is a logistic one. In other words, by considering two loci, we have:

$$\text{Eq. 74} \quad \begin{cases} \log\left(\frac{P(Y=1|X_1=x)}{P(Y=0|X_1=x)}\right) = \beta_0^{(1)} + \beta_1^{(1)}x_1, & x_1 = 0, 1, 2 \\ \log\left(\frac{P(Y=1|X_2=x)}{P(Y=0|X_2=x)}\right) = \beta_0^{(2)} + \beta_1^{(2)}x_2, & x_2 = 0, 1, 2 \end{cases}$$

which leads to

$$\text{Eq. 75} \quad \begin{cases} \beta_1^{(1)} = \log(OR_1) \\ \beta_1^{(2)} = \log(OR_2) \end{cases}$$

If we express Eq. 73 as a function of $\beta_1^{(1)}, \beta_1^{(2)}$ we have

$$e^{\beta_1^{(2)}} - 1 = \frac{(e^{\beta_1^{(1)}} - 1)d}{\left(f(B) + (e^{\beta_1^{(1)}} - 1)(f(a)f(B) - d)\right)f(b)}$$

Note now that for values of OR_1 close to 1, $\beta_1^{(1)}$ is close to zero and we can use the approximations

$$\text{Eq. 76} \quad e^{\beta_1^{(i)}} - 1 \sim \beta_1^{(i)} \quad i = 1, 2$$

and we get

$$\beta_1^{(2)} = \frac{\beta_1^{(1)}d}{\left(f(B) + \beta_1^{(1)}(f(a)f(B) - d)\right)f(b)} = \frac{\beta_1^{(1)}\rho\sqrt{f(A)f(a)f(B)}}{\left(f(B) + \beta_1^{(1)}(f(a)f(B) - d)\right)\sqrt{f(b)}}$$

If we make the further approximation

$$\text{Eq. 77} \quad \beta_1^{(1)}(f(a)f(B) - d) \ll f(B) \Rightarrow f(B) + \beta_1^{(1)}(f(a)f(B) - d) \sim f(B)$$

we conclude that

$$\text{Eq. 78} \quad \beta_1^{(2)} = \beta_1^{(1)} \rho \sqrt{\frac{f(A)f(a)}{f(B)f(b)}}$$

This is the formula derived by Matti Pirinen in his lessons on GWAS at the University of Helsinki (page 11 of topic 7, [R](#)). For further details see also ([Maccallini P. 2022](#)).

4.7.2 A numerical example

We consider the variant 13:41353297:G:A from Table 12 (comparison between healthy UK citizens and females affected by self-reported chronic fatigue syndrome, phenotype 20002_1482). We build the table below, where we have added the subscripts D, H to distinguish between frequencies of the major allele in patients (D) and controls (H). We then consider variant 13:41404706:T:C as locus L_2 . We find the correlation coefficient

$$\rho^2 = 0.769135 \Rightarrow \rho = \pm 0.8770$$

Note that $\beta_1^{(1)}$ as been calculated for the alternative allele A and since it is negative, we can say that the reference allele is the one that predisposes to the disease in this case.

L_1	L_2
13:41353297:G:A	13:41404706:T:C
$f_D(A) = 0.4478$	$f_D(C) = 0.4246$
$f_H(A) = 0.5057$	$f_H(C) = 0.4864$
$\beta_1^{(1)} = -1.40 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-
$\rho^2 = 0.769135$	

By using Eq. 78 we can then calculate

$$\beta_1^{(2)} = \beta_1^{(1)} \rho \sqrt{\frac{f_H(A)f_H(G)}{f_H(C)f_H(T)}} = \mp 1.40 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot 0,8770 \sqrt{\frac{0.5057(1 - 0.5057)}{0.4864(1 - 0.4864)}} = \mp 1.23 \cdot 10^{-3}$$

where the sign is plus if $\rho < 0$ and it is minus if $\rho > 0$. It must be noted though that Eq. 78 has been built by considering $\beta_1^{(2)}$ calculated with respect to the allele positively correlated with the one that predisposes to the disease or the one that protects against the disease. Then we conclude that $\beta_1^{(2)} = -1.23 \cdot 10^{-3}$. We can't say which one is the allele of L_2 that is positively correlated with the protective allele A , though. On the other hand, we know from ([Vukcevic D 2009](#)) that it must be

$$\text{Eq. 79} \quad -f(a)f(b) \leq d \leq f(B)f(a) \Leftrightarrow -\sqrt{\frac{f(a)f(b)}{f(A)f(B)}} \leq \rho \leq \sqrt{\frac{f(B)f(a)}{f(b)f(A)}}$$

where the LD is calculated between the two major alleles (or the two minor ones) and where we have assumed $f(a) \leq f(A), f(b) \leq f(B), f(a) \leq f(b)$. In our case, we have

$$f(a) = f_H(C), f(b) = f_H(G) \Rightarrow$$

$$-0.9621 = -\sqrt{\frac{f_H(C)f_H(G)}{(1-f_H(C))(1-f_H(G))}} \leq \rho \leq \sqrt{\frac{(1-f_H(G))f_H(C)}{f_H(G)(1-f_H(C))}} = 0.9843$$

RS Number	Position (GRCh37)	Allele Frequencies	Haplotypes			
rs7337312	chr13:41353297	G=0.516, A=0.483	G	A	A	G
rs11147812	chr13:41404706	T=0.544, C=0.456	T	C	T	C
Haplotype Count			91	80	8	3
Haplotype Frequency			0.5	0.4396	0.044	0.0165

So Eq. 79 does not allow a determination of the sign of ρ . In this case, we must retrieve the frequencies of the haplotypes from experimental data and calculate ρ . To do so, we go to LDlink ([click](#)) and select the function LDhap. We then select the reference genome we are dealing with (GRCh37), the population we are interested in (European, GBR), and the pair of variants. The output is reported above. Therefore, we have:

$$\text{Eq. 80} \quad \begin{cases} f_H(G, T) = 0.5 \\ f_H(G) = 0.516 \\ f_H(T) = 0.544 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \rho = \frac{f_H(G, T) - f_H(G)f_H(T)}{\sqrt{f_H(G)(1-f_H(G))f_H(T)(1-f_H(T))}} = 0.8810$$

It follows then that the reference alleles are positively correlated (so the alternative ones are positively correlated too). The small discrepancy in the value of ρ with the previous one is due probably to the fact that I retrieved it for another reference genome (GRCh38). The frequencies of the alleles in the control group are different too because these are different control groups. All that said we can now calculate the effect size $\beta_1^{(2)}$ relative to the alternate allele C and we have:

$$\text{Eq. 81} \quad \beta_1^{(2)} = \beta_1^{(1)} \rho \sqrt{\frac{f_H(A)f_H(G)}{f_H(C)f_H(T)}} = -1.40 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot 0.8810 \sqrt{\frac{0.5057(1-0.5057)}{0.4864(1-0.4864)}} = -1.24 \cdot 10^{-3}$$

This effect size is enough, in this case, to give a positive correlation between the disease and the variant in L_2 . Yet, if L_1 was the true causal locus, we would erroneously assume that L_2 is causal too. So, this shows how it is important to develop a way to take into account the contribution to effect size given by linkage disequilibrium with the true causal variant. If we had used Eq. 73 we would have had

$$OR_2 - 1 = \frac{(OR_1 - 1)d}{f_H(C)[f_H(T) + (OR_1 - 1)(f_H(A)f_H(G) - d)]} = -1.0578 \cdot 10^{-3} \Rightarrow$$

$$\Rightarrow \begin{cases} OR_2 = 0.9989 \\ \beta_1^{(2)} = -1.0584 \cdot 10^{-3} \end{cases}$$

where we have considered that

$$d = \rho \sqrt{f_H(G)(1 - f_H(G))f_H(C)(1 - f_H(C))} = 0.2202$$

$$\beta_1^{(1)} = \log(OR_1) \Rightarrow OR_1 = e^{\beta_1^{(1)}} = 0.9988$$

Figure 9. The error that we have for $\beta_1^{(2)}$ when we use Eq. 78 instead of Eq. 73, for $OR_1 \in [0.2, 1.8]$.

Figure 10. Left: the error in Eq. 82 as a function of ρ for the numerical example in par. 4.7.2. Right: plot of $\beta_1^{(2)}$ when we use Eq. 78 instead of Eq. 73 as a function of the admissible values of ρ for the same numerical example.

This discrepancy between these two formulae would require a more accurate study, by analyzing the extremes of the module of their difference, as a function of the frequencies of the two major [minor] alleles and d or ρ (with the condition in Eq. 79). We can easily solve this problem numerically, though, by calculating:

$$\text{Eq. 82} \quad \varepsilon = \left| \beta_1^{(1)} \rho \sqrt{\frac{f(A)f(a)}{f(B)f(b)}} - \ln(OR_2) \right|$$

with OR_2 given by Eq. 73 and with the restrains of Eq. 79, for $f_H(a) \in [0,0.5]$, $f_H(b) \in [0,0.5]$. In particular, if we consider the range $OR_1 \in [0.2,1.8]$ we have for ε the plot in Figure 9 and its maximum value is 0.3128. If we plot this same error in the case of our numerical example as a function of ρ , we have the plots in Figure 10. These calculations have been performed by the following two scripts.

4.7.2.1 Script

This is the Octave script that plots Figure 9.

```
% file name = effect_size
% date of creation = 10/05/2022
clear all
close all
%-----
% arraies for f_a, f_A, f_b, f_B
%-----
step = 0.02;
f_a = [0:step:0.5];
f_A = 1 - f_a;
f_b = f_a;
f_B = 1 - f_b;
%-----
% arraies for OR_1
%-----
OR_1 = [0.2:step:1.8];
%-----
% values for beta2 given OR1 (approximated and exact formula)
%-----
module = 0;
module_2(1:length(OR_1)) = 0;
beta_ap = 0;
beta_an = 0;
p = 1;
for i=1:length(f_a)
    for j=1:length(f_b)
        if (f_a(i) < f_b(j))
            d = [-f_a(i)*f_b(j):step:f_B(j)*f_a(i)];
            rho = d/sqrt(f_a(i)*f_A(i)*f_b(j)*f_B(j));
        else
            d = [-f_a(i)*f_b(j):step:f_b(j)*f_A(i)];
            rho = d/sqrt(f_a(i)*f_A(i)*f_b(j)*f_B(j));
        endif
        for k=1:length(d)
            for h=1:length(OR_1)
                beta_ap(i,j,k,h) = log(OR_1(h))*rho(k)*sqrt((f_A(i)*f_a(i))/(f_b(j)*f_B(j)));
                num = (OR_1(h) - 1)*d(k);
                den = f_b(j)*(f_B(j) + (OR_1(h) - 1)*(f_a(i)*f_B(j) - d(k)));
                OR_2 = 1 + num/den;
                beta_an(i,j,k,h) = log(OR_2);
                module(p) = abs(beta_ap(i,j,k,h)-beta_an(i,j,k,h));
                if (module(p)>module_2(h))
                    module_2(h) = module(p);
                endif
                p = p+1;
            endfor
        endfor
    endfor
endfor
```

```

    endfor
    clear d rho
  endfor
endfor
plot(OR_1,module_2,'-k', 'linewidth',2)
grid minor
xlabel('OR_{1}','fontsize',15);
ylabel('{\epsilon}','fontsize',15);
max(module)

```

4.7.2.2 Script

This is the Octave script that plots Figure 10.

```

% file name = effect_size_2
% date of creation = 10/05/2022
clear all
close all
%-----
% data
%-----
f_a = 0.5057;           % alternative at locus 1
f_A = 1 - f_a;         % reference at locus 1
f_b = 0.4864;         % alternative at locus 2
f_B = 1 - f_b;         % reference at locus 2
OR_1 = 0.9988;         % with respect to the alternative
step = 0.01;
%-----
% array for d and rho
%-----
if (f_a < f_A)
  if (f_b < f_B)
    if (f_a < f_b)
      d = [-f_a*f_b:step:f_B*f_a];
      rho = d/sqrt(f_a*f_A*f_b*f_B);
    else
      d = [-f_a*f_b:step:f_b*f_A];
      rho = d/sqrt(f_a*f_A*f_b*f_B);
    endif
  else
    if (f_a < f_B)
      d = [-f_a*f_B:step:f_b*f_a];
      rho = d/sqrt(f_a*f_A*f_B*f_b);
    else
      d = [-f_a*f_B:step:f_B*f_A];
      rho = d/sqrt(f_a*f_A*f_B*f_b);
    endif
  endif
else
  if (f_b < f_B)
    if (f_A < f_b)
      d = [-f_A*f_b:step:f_B*f_A];
      rho = d/sqrt(f_A*f_a*f_b*f_B);
    else
      d = [-f_A*f_b:step:f_b*f_a];
      rho = d/sqrt(f_A*f_a*f_b*f_B);
    endif
  endif
endif

```

```

else
  if (f_A < f_B)
    d = [-f_A*f_B:step:f_b*f_A];
    rho = d/sqrt(f_a*f_A*f_B*f_b);
  else
    d = [-f_A*f_B:step:f_B*f_a];
    rho = d/sqrt(f_A*f_a*f_B*f_b);
  endif
endif
endif
%-----
% array for epsilon
for k=1:length(d)
  beta_ap(k) = log(OR_1)*rho(k)*sqrt((f_A*f_a)/(f_b*f_B));
  num = (OR_1 - 1)*d(k);
  den = f_b*(f_B + (OR_1 - 1)*(f_a*f_B - d(k)));
  OR_2 = 1 + num/den;
  beta_an(k) = log(OR_2);
  module(k) = abs(beta_ap(k)-beta_an(k));
endfor
figure(1)
plot(rho,module,'-k', 'linewidth',2)
grid minor
xlabel('\rho','fontsize',15);
ylabel('\epsilon','fontsize',15);
figure(2)
plot(rho,beta_ap,'-k', 'linewidth',1)
hold on
plot(rho,beta_an,'--k', 'linewidth',1)
grid minor
xlabel('\rho','fontsize',15);
ylabel('\beta^{(2)}','fontsize',15);
legend('approximation', 'exact','fontsize',15);

```

4.8 Fine mapping

If the effect size of a variant is influenced by the effect size of the variants it is correlated with, what is the true causal effect? To carry out our discussions it is preferable to indicate with λ_i the causal effect size associated with locus L_i , while β_i indicates the effect size due to correlation with causal loci (*marginal effect*). By using Eq. 78 we can write

$$\text{Eq. 83} \quad \beta_j = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \rho_{ij} \sqrt{\frac{f_i(1-f_i)}{f_j(1-f_j)}}$$

where f_i is the minor allele frequency⁶ at locus L_i and ρ_{ij} is the correlation between loci L_i, L_j . Note that if λ_i are calculated with respect to the alternative allele, then ρ_{ij} must be the correlation between the alternative alleles or between the reference ones. The result of a GWAS gives the marginal effects β_1, β_2, \dots while we are interested in the causal ones $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots$. We can write the following linear system:

⁶ Or the major allele frequency, or the alternative one, or the reference one. The result does not change.

$$\text{Eq. 84} \quad \boldsymbol{\beta} = M\boldsymbol{\lambda} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \beta_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12}\sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} & \cdots & \rho_{1n}\sqrt{\frac{f_n(1-f_n)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \\ \rho_{21}\sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} & 1 & \cdots & \rho_{2n}\sqrt{\frac{f_n(1-f_n)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_{n1}\sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_n(1-f_n)}} & \rho_{n2}\sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_n(1-f_n)}} & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 \\ \lambda_2 \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_n \end{bmatrix}$$

If the determinant of the matrix is different from zero, we conclude that the causal effects are

$$\text{Eq. 85} \quad \boldsymbol{\lambda} = M^{-1}\boldsymbol{\beta} \Leftrightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 \\ \lambda_2 \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12}\sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} & \cdots & \rho_{1n}\sqrt{\frac{f_n(1-f_n)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \\ \rho_{21}\sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} & 1 & \cdots & \rho_{2n}\sqrt{\frac{f_n(1-f_n)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_{n1}\sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_n(1-f_n)}} & \rho_{n2}\sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_n(1-f_n)}} & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \beta_n \end{bmatrix}$$

Note that from Eq. 79 we deduce that

$$\text{Eq. 86} \quad \begin{cases} -\sqrt{\frac{f_i f_j}{(1-f_i)(1-f_j)}} \leq \rho_{i,j} \leq \sqrt{\frac{(1-f_j)f_i}{f_j(1-f_i)}} \leftarrow f_i \leq f_j \\ -\sqrt{\frac{f_i f_j}{(1-f_i)(1-f_j)}} \leq \rho_{i,j} \leq \sqrt{\frac{(1-f_i)f_j}{f_i(1-f_j)}} \leftarrow f_j \leq f_i \end{cases}$$

where we have assumed that f_i, f_j are the frequencies of the minor alleles. This means that

$$\text{Eq. 87} \quad \begin{cases} -\frac{f_i}{(1-f_j)} \leq \rho_{i,j} \sqrt{\frac{f_i(1-f_i)}{f_j(1-f_j)}} \leq \frac{f_i}{f_j} \leftarrow f_i \leq f_j \\ -\frac{f_i}{(1-f_j)} \leq \rho_{i,j} \sqrt{\frac{f_i(1-f_i)}{f_j(1-f_j)}} \leq \frac{(1-f_i)}{(1-f_j)} \leftarrow f_j \leq f_i \end{cases} \Rightarrow -1 \leq \rho_{i,j} \sqrt{\frac{f_i(1-f_i)}{f_j(1-f_j)}} \leq 1$$

In other words, the elements of the matrix associated with the linear system in Eq. 84 must belong to the interval $[-1,1]$. As for the determinant, if we had only two loci we would have

$$\det \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12}\sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \\ \rho_{21}\sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} & 1 \end{bmatrix} = 1 - \rho_{12}\rho_{21}\sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}}\sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} = 1 - \rho_{12}^2 \geq 0$$

So we have zero when L_1, L_2 are in complete disequilibrium. For three loci we have

$$\begin{vmatrix}
1 & \rho_{12} \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} & \rho_{13} \sqrt{\frac{f_3(1-f_3)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \\
\rho_{21} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} & 1 & \rho_{23} \sqrt{\frac{f_3(1-f_3)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} \\
\rho_{31} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_3(1-f_3)}} & \rho_{32} \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_3(1-f_3)}} & 1
\end{vmatrix} = 1 - \rho_{23}^2 - \rho_{12}(\rho_{21} - \rho_{23}\rho_{31}) + \\
+ \rho_{13}(\rho_{21}\rho_{32} - \rho_{31}) = 1 - \rho_{23}^2 - \rho_{21}^2 - \rho_{31}^2 + 2\rho_{12}\rho_{23}\rho_{31}$$

And so forth. Is it possible to find a general formula for the determinant of M ? We note that

$$\begin{aligned}
\det(M) &= \begin{vmatrix} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} & \rho_{12} \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \\ \rho_{21} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} & \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} \end{vmatrix} = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} \sqrt{f_1(1-f_1)} & \rho_{12} \sqrt{f_2(1-f_2)} \\ \rho_{21} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} & \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} \end{vmatrix}}{\sqrt{f_1(1-f_1)}} = \\
&= \frac{\begin{vmatrix} \sqrt{f_1(1-f_1)} & \rho_{12} \sqrt{f_2(1-f_2)} \\ \rho_{21} \sqrt{f_1(1-f_1)} & \sqrt{f_2(1-f_2)} \end{vmatrix}}{\sqrt{f_1(1-f_1)} \sqrt{f_2(1-f_2)}} = \sqrt{f_1(1-f_1)} \frac{\begin{vmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12} \sqrt{f_2(1-f_2)} \\ \rho_{21} & \sqrt{f_2(1-f_2)} \end{vmatrix}}{\sqrt{f_1(1-f_1)} \sqrt{f_2(1-f_2)}} = \\
&= \sqrt{f_1(1-f_1)} \sqrt{f_2(1-f_2)} \frac{\begin{vmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12} \\ \rho_{21} & 1 \end{vmatrix}}{\sqrt{f_1(1-f_1)} \sqrt{f_2(1-f_2)}} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12} \\ \rho_{21} & 1 \end{vmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

And it is easy to recognize that in general

$$\text{Eq. 88} \quad \det(M) = \det \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12} & \dots & \rho_{1n} \\ \rho_{21} & 1 & \dots & \rho_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_{n1} & \rho_{n2} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

4.8.1 Standard error of the causal effect

The marginal effects β_1, β_2, \dots are estimators of the means of the true marginal effects and they have their standard errors (which are included in GWAS summary statistics). What about the standard errors for $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots$? Since the standard error is the standard deviation of the density of the mean of an estimator, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \begin{bmatrix} \text{Var}[\beta_1] \\ \text{Var}[\beta_2] \\ \vdots \\ \text{Var}[\beta_n] \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12}^2 \frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)} & \cdots & \rho_{1n}^2 \frac{f_n(1-f_n)}{f_1(1-f_1)} \\ \rho_{21}^2 \frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)} & 1 & \cdots & \rho_{2n}^2 \frac{f_n(1-f_n)}{f_2(1-f_2)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_{n1}^2 \frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_n(1-f_n)} & \rho_{n2}^2 \frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_n(1-f_n)} & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \text{Var}[\lambda_1] \\ \text{Var}[\lambda_2] \\ \vdots \\ \text{Var}[\lambda_n] \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow \\
\text{Eq. 89} \quad & \begin{bmatrix} SE^2[\hat{\beta}_1] \\ SE^2[\hat{\beta}_2] \\ \vdots \\ SE^2[\hat{\beta}_n] \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12}^2 \frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)} & \cdots & \rho_{1n}^2 \frac{f_n(1-f_n)}{f_1(1-f_1)} \\ \rho_{21}^2 \frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)} & 1 & \cdots & \rho_{2n}^2 \frac{f_n(1-f_n)}{f_2(1-f_2)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_{n1}^2 \frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_n(1-f_n)} & \rho_{n2}^2 \frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_n(1-f_n)} & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} SE^2[\hat{\lambda}_1] \\ SE^2[\hat{\lambda}_2] \\ \vdots \\ SE^2[\hat{\lambda}_n] \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

where we mean that $\hat{\lambda}_i$ is the estimator for the causal effect and $\hat{\beta}_i$ is the estimator for the marginal effect. Therefore, we can write

$$\text{Eq. 90} \quad \begin{bmatrix} SE^2[\hat{\lambda}_1] \\ SE^2[\hat{\lambda}_2] \\ \vdots \\ SE^2[\hat{\lambda}_n] \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12}^2 \frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)} & \cdots & \rho_{1n}^2 \frac{f_n(1-f_n)}{f_1(1-f_1)} \\ \rho_{21}^2 \frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)} & 1 & \cdots & \rho_{2n}^2 \frac{f_n(1-f_n)}{f_2(1-f_2)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho_{n1}^2 \frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_n(1-f_n)} & \rho_{n2}^2 \frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_n(1-f_n)} & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} SE^2[\hat{\beta}_1] \\ SE^2[\hat{\beta}_2] \\ \vdots \\ SE^2[\hat{\beta}_n] \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore, the standard errors of the causal effects are calculated by solving the linear system above and by extracting the square root of the solution. But the reader might have noticed that this method does not grant that we get positive values for $SE^2[\hat{\lambda}_i]$ and it is not clear what should we do with negative values. Another possible way to calculate $SE[\hat{\lambda}_i]$ is to consider that according to the central limit theorem we have

$$\text{Eq. 91} \quad \beta_i \sim N(\hat{\beta}_i, SE^2[\hat{\beta}_i]), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots$$

we can then generate a normal random vector for β according to and obtain a distribution for λ . We then compute the standard deviation for each component of λ . This method has a high computational cost. Let us then consider a further approach and introduce it considering the case of two loci only:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12} \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \\ \rho_{21} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{\rho_{21}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} \\ -\frac{\rho_{12}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} & 1 \end{bmatrix}^T =$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{\rho_{12}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \\ -\frac{\rho_{21}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore the causal effects are

$$\begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 \\ \lambda_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{\rho_{12}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \\ -\frac{\rho_{21}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 - \frac{\rho_{12}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \beta_2 \\ -\frac{\rho_{21}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} \beta_1 + \beta_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

But we know that by the central limit theorem the estimates of λ_1, λ_2 have a normal density with a mean of $\hat{\lambda}_1, \hat{\lambda}_2$ respectively. Note now that

$$\beta_2 \sim N(\hat{\beta}_2, SE^2[\hat{\beta}_2]) \Rightarrow X_{1,2} = -\frac{\rho_{12}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \beta_2 \sim N\left(\hat{\beta}_2, \frac{\rho_{12}^2 SE^2[\hat{\beta}_2] f_2(1-f_2)}{(1-\rho_{12}^2)^2 f_1(1-f_1)}\right)$$

We also know that $\beta_1 \sim N(\hat{\beta}_1, SE^2[\hat{\beta}_1])$. Therefore, we can compute the law for λ_1 :

$$\lambda_1 \sim N\left(\hat{\beta}_1 - \frac{\rho_{12}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_2(1-f_2)}{f_1(1-f_1)}} \hat{\beta}_2, SE^2[\hat{\beta}_1] + \frac{\rho_{12}^2 f_2(1-f_2)}{(1-\rho_{12}^2)^2 f_1(1-f_1)} SE^2[\hat{\beta}_2]\right)$$

Analogously, we find

$$\lambda_2 \sim N\left(-\frac{\rho_{21}}{1-\rho_{12}^2} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1-f_1)}{f_2(1-f_2)}} \hat{\beta}_1 + \hat{\beta}_2, \frac{\rho_{21}^2 f_1(1-f_1)}{(1-\rho_{12}^2)^2 f_2(1-f_2)} SE^2[\hat{\beta}_1] + SE^2[\hat{\beta}_2]\right)$$

In other words, if we indicate $a_{i,j}$ the generic element of M^{-1} we have

$$\text{Eq. 92} \quad \lambda_i \sim N\left(\sum_{j=1}^n a_{i,j} \hat{\beta}_j, \sum_{j=1}^n a_{i,j}^2 SE^2[\hat{\beta}_j]\right)$$

From this, it follows that

$$\text{Eq. 93} \quad SE[\hat{\lambda}_i] = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n a_{i,j}^2 SE^2[\hat{\beta}_j]}$$

4.8.2 P values for causal effects

If we assume that the statistics of the causal effect is the same statistics of the marginal effect, we have that under the null hypothesis $\hat{\lambda}_i/SE[\hat{\lambda}_i]$ has a standard normal distribution. Therefore the p value associated with the causal effect of the i^{th} variant is given by

$$\text{Eq. 94} \quad p_i = 2P\left(z < -\frac{|\hat{\lambda}_i|}{SE[\hat{\lambda}_i]}\right) = 2\Phi\left(-\frac{|\hat{\lambda}_i|}{SE[\hat{\lambda}_i]}\right)$$

4.8.3 Preconditioned Conjugate Gradient

To solve the linear systems in Eq. 85 and Eq. 90 we use the Octave built-in function `pcg` that is based on the preconditioned conjugate gradient iterative method ([Ref](#)). It calculates vector λ of the equation $\beta = M\lambda$ and it requires that M is both symmetric and positive definite. Note though that the matrices associated with Eq. 85 and Eq. 90 are in general not-symmetric. Yet, if we consider the equivalent system $M^T\beta = M^TM\lambda$ we see that its associated matrix M^TM is both symmetric and positive definite. First of all, M^TM is symmetric:

$$(M^TM)^T = M^T(M^T)^T = M^TM$$

Moreover, it is positive definite:

$$Y^T(M^TM)Y = (Y^TM^T)(MY) = (MY)^T(MY) \geq 0, \quad \forall Y \in \mathbb{R}^n$$

So, we will solve the system $M^T\beta = M^TM\lambda$ instead of the one in Eq. 85 and the same will be done for the system in Eq. 90. I will also check the result by using use the function `LinearSolve` of Mathematica 5.2 on the matrices associated with the linear systems in Eq. 85 and Eq. 90.

4.8.3.1 Note on the inverse matrix

To calculate the standard errors for the causal effects, we can't avoid calculating M^{-1} . Octave has its own built-in function for the inverse of a matrix, but a comparison with Mathematica 5.2 for the inverse of the matrix in Table 42 shows inconsistency in the result. I present here an iterative method that can be implemented in Octave for calculating the inverse of M with a result comparable with the output of Mathematica 5.2. Note that if I indicate X_i the i^{th} column of M^{-1} we can write

$$MM^{-1} = I \Rightarrow MX_i = E_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

where E_i is the i^{th} column of the identity matrix I . This reduces the problem of calculating M^{-1} to the solution of n linear systems. We can then use the preconditioned conjugate gradient iterative method for each one of these systems by considering the equivalent systems:

$$\text{Eq. 95} \quad M^TMX_i = M^TE_i \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

4.8.4 First Numerical Application (phenotype 20002_1482, females)

We consider again the experimental data mentioned in par. 4.7.2 and Table 12. The summary statistics produced by Neale's Lab found eleven variants significantly associated with the phenotype 20002_1482 in female subjects, once we remove variants with minor allele frequency below 0.05 (see Table 38). If we interrogate LDhap with column 2 of the table, with reference genome GRCh37,

and reference population GBR (British in England and Scotland) we get the haplotypes in the table below. In both the tables, loci are displaced according to their position on chromosome 13: from the lower position to the higher. How do we calculate the correlation parameters from this table in an automated fashion? We first have to calculate the frequencies of all the possible haplotypes of two loci. Let us consider the first two loci: we need $f(A-)$ and this haplotype is present in three lines. We have:

$$f(A-) = f_{1,2} = 0.4231 + 0.033 + 0.0055 = 0.4611 \Rightarrow d_{12} = f(A-) - f(A)f(-) = 0.2211 \Rightarrow$$

$$\Rightarrow \rho_{12} = \frac{d}{\sqrt{f(A)f(-)(1-f(A))(1-f(-))}} = 0.8858$$

where the frequencies of the alternative alleles in controls have been retrieved from column 6 of Table 38. If we had used the frequencies from the general GBR population (Table 40) we would have had

$$d_{12} = 0.2379 \Rightarrow \rho_{12} = 0.9551$$

Variant (h19)	rsid	beta	pval	Alt_AF_cases	Alt_AF_controls
chr13:41353297	rs7337312	-1.403E-03	2.56E-08	0.4478	0.5057
chr13:41358365	rs368309529	-1.514E-03	2.92E-09	0.4139	0.4745
chr13:41358369	rs564453195	-1.514E-03	2.92E-09	0.4139	0.4745
chr13:41363595	rs7997189	-1.391E-03	3.50E-08	0.4464	0.5035
chr13:41369790	rs1536807	-1.449E-03	9.55E-09	0.4499	0.5092
chr13:41370996	rs6563846	-1.456E-03	7.74E-09	0.4538	0.5135
chr13:41374328	rs2282023	-1.457E-03	7.49E-09	0.4538	0.5136
chr13:41381077	rs2282026	-1.456E-03	7.75E-09	0.4536	0.5133
chr13:41387065	rs2017696	-1.492E-03	3.41E-09	0.4537	0.5148
chr13:41390881	rs7330720	-1.485E-03	4.02E-09	0.4537	0.5145
chr13:41404706	rs11147812	-1.530E-03	1.63E-09	0.4246	0.4864

Table 38. Statistically significant correlation between phenotype 20002_1482 (females only) and variants. Note that these variants are all close one to the other, which raises suspicion that many of these variants are not causal ones. The variant with the lowest p value is highlighted.

Note that since $\rho_{12} = \rho_{21}$ we don't have to calculate ρ_{21} . So the next calculation would be between loci L_1 and L_3 , and so forth until we reach the couple L_1, L_{11} . Then we start with L_2, L_3 (since L_2, L_1 has already been considered) and so forth. Let us try another one, the one in par. 4.7.2 which is L_1, L_{11} :

$$f(AC) = f_{1,11} = \frac{77 + 2 + 1}{182} = 0.4396 \Rightarrow d_{1,11} = f(AC) - f(A)f(C) =$$

$$= 0.4396 - 0.483 \cdot 0.456 = 0.2193 \Rightarrow \rho_{1,11} = \frac{d}{\sqrt{f(A)f(C)(1-f(A))(1-f(C))}} = 0.8812$$

haplotype	count	frequency
T_T_T_A_A_C_G_T_G_T	91	0.5
-_C_C_G_G_G_A_A_A_C	77	0.4231
-_C_C_G_G_G_A_A_A_T	6	0.033
T_T_T_G_G_G_A_A_A_C	3	0.0165
T_T_C_G_G_G_A_A_A_C	2	0.011
T_T_C_G_G_G_A_A_A_T	2	0.011
-_C_C_A_G_G_A_A_A_C	1	0.0055

Table 39. Frequencies of all the haplotypes present in the GBR population, when we consider the variants collected in Table 38.

RS_Number	Position (hg19)	Ref AF	Alt AF
rs7337312	chr13:41353297	G=0.516,	A=0.483
rs368309529	chr13:41358365	T=0.538,	-=0.462
rs564453195	chr13:41358369	T=0.538,	C=0.462
rs7997189	chr13:41363595	T=0.516,	C=0.483
rs1536807	chr13:41369790	A=0.505,	G=0.494
rs6563846	chr13:41370996	A=0.500,	G=0.500
rs2282023	chr13:41374328	C=0.500,	G=0.500
rs2282026	chr13:41381077	G=0.500,	A=0.500
rs2017696	chr13:41387065	T=0.500,	A=0.500
rs7330720	chr13:41390881	G=0.500,	A=0.500
rs11147812	chr13:41404706	T=0.544,	C=0.456

Table 40. Allele frequencies for the variants in Table 38 from the GBR population.

	L_1	L_2	L_3	L_4	L_5	L_6	L_7	L_8	L_9	L_{10}	L_{11}
L_1	1.0000	0.8877	0.8877	0.9157	0.8823	0.8958	0.8956	0.8961	0.8932	0.8938	0.7747
L_2	0.8877	1.0000	0.9482	0.8918	0.8591	0.8731	0.8729	0.8734	0.8707	0.8713	0.7925
L_3	0.8877	0.9482	1.0000	0.8918	0.8591	0.8731	0.8729	0.8734	0.8707	0.8713	0.7925
L_4	0.9157	0.8918	0.8918	1.0000	0.8868	0.9002	0.9001	0.9006	0.8977	0.8983	0.7790
L_5	0.8823	0.8591	0.8591	0.8868	1.0000	0.9326	0.9324	0.9329	0.9301	0.9307	0.8120
L_6	0.8958	0.8731	0.8731	0.9002	0.9326	1.0000	0.9458	0.9463	0.9434	0.9440	0.8257
L_7	0.8956	0.8729	0.8729	0.9001	0.9324	0.9458	1.0000	0.9461	0.9432	0.9438	0.8256
L_8	0.8961	0.8734	0.8734	0.9006	0.9329	0.9463	0.9461	1.0000	0.9437	0.9443	0.8260
L_9	0.8932	0.8707	0.8707	0.8977	0.9301	0.9434	0.9432	0.9437	1.0000	0.9414	0.8233
L_{10}	0.8938	0.8713	0.8713	0.8983	0.9307	0.9440	0.9438	0.9443	0.9414	1.0000	0.8239
L_{11}	0.7747	0.7925	0.7925	0.7790	0.8120	0.8257	0.8256	0.8260	0.8233	0.8239	1.0000

Table 41. Linkage disequilibrium measured as $\rho_{i,j}$ between each possible couple of the loci in Table 38. This calculation is based on the allele frequencies of the control group in Table 38, while the frequencies of each possible binary haplotype were calculated from data collected in Table 39.

In this case, we have used the count of the haplotypes (column 2) instead of their frequencies and we have used as frequencies of the alleles the ones that come from the same population Table 39 has been calculated from (collected in Table 40) and we get a result comparable to the one in Eq. 80. Note that the correlation parameter for each locus should be calculated by using the haplotype frequencies and allele frequencies from the same population that has been used as a control group for the determination of the effect sizes β_1, β_2, \dots . But if we only have GWAS summary statistics, it is not

possible to calculate the haplotype frequencies of the binary haplotypes, because we only have the frequencies of the alleles in the control group. So we are compelled to use the frequencies of the binary haplotypes from a similar population and then we must choose between the allele frequencies of that same population or the one of the control group provided by the summary statistics.

1.0000	0.8866	0.8866	0.9158	0.8822	0.8955	0.8953	0.8958	0.8929	0.8935	0.7745
0.8888	1.0000	0.9482	0.8929	0.8600	0.8739	0.8737	0.8742	0.8714	0.8720	0.7933
0.8888	0.9482	1.0000	0.8929	0.8600	0.8739	0.8737	0.8742	0.8714	0.8720	0.7933
0.9157	0.8907	0.8907	1.0000	0.8866	0.8999	0.8998	0.9003	0.8974	0.8980	0.7787
0.8824	0.8581	0.8581	0.8869	1.0000	0.9324	0.9323	0.9328	0.9298	0.9304	0.8118
0.8960	0.8722	0.8722	0.9005	0.9328	1.0000	0.9458	0.9463	0.9433	0.9439	0.8257
0.8959	0.8721	0.8721	0.9004	0.9326	0.9458	1.0000	0.9461	0.9431	0.9438	0.8256
0.8963	0.8725	0.8725	0.9009	0.9331	0.9462	0.9461	1.0000	0.9436	0.9443	0.8260
0.8936	0.8699	0.8699	0.8981	0.9303	0.9434	0.9433	0.9438	1.0000	0.9414	0.8234
0.8941	0.8705	0.8705	0.8987	0.9309	0.9440	0.9439	0.9444	0.9414	1.0000	0.8239
0.7750	0.7918	0.7918	0.7793	0.8121	0.8257	0.8256	0.8260	0.8232	0.8238	1.0000

Table 42. Matrix associated with the linear system in Eq. 84.

Figure 11. The module of the residual of the preconditioned conjugate gradient iterative method applied to the linear system in Eq. 85 for the numerical example of par. 4.8.4 as a function of the number of iterations.

The following calculations are performed by the script in par. 4.8.8. It uses data collected in Table 38, Table 39, and Table 40. By using the haplotype frequencies in Table 39 and the allele frequencies for the control group in Table 38, it calculates the matrix for the values $\rho_{i,j}$ collected in Table 41. As a quality test, let's us check manually some of these values:

$$f_{1,3} = f(A, C) = \frac{77 + 6 + 1}{182} = 0.4615 \Rightarrow$$

$$\Rightarrow \rho_{1,3} = \rho_{3,1} = \frac{0.4615 - 0.5057 \cdot 0.4745}{\sqrt{0.5057(1 - 0.5057)0.4745(1 - 0.4745)}} = 0.8874$$

$$f_{3,8} = f(C,A) = \frac{77 + 6 + 1}{182} = 0.4615 \Rightarrow$$

$$\Rightarrow \rho_{3,8} = \rho_{8,3} = \frac{0.4615 - 0.5133 \cdot 0.4745}{\sqrt{0.5133(1 - 0.5133)0.4745(1 - 0.4745)}} = 0.8732$$

$$f_{4,5} = f(C,G) = \frac{77 + 6 + 2 + 2}{182} = 0.4780 \Rightarrow$$

$$\Rightarrow \rho_{4,5} = \rho_{5,4} = \frac{0.4780 - 0.5035 \cdot 0.5092}{\sqrt{0.5035(1 - 0.5035)0.5092(1 - 0.5092)}} = 0.8866$$

The script then calculates the matrix associated with the linear system in Eq. 84 by using the alternative allele frequencies of the control group (from Table 38). This matrix is the one in Table 42. We manually calculate some of its cells as a quality check:

Figure 12. The error that we have for $\beta_1^{(2)}$ when we use Eq. 78 instead of Eq. 73, for $OR_1 \in [0.9985, 1.0015]$.

$$m_{1,3} = \rho_{1,3} \sqrt{\frac{f_3(1 - f_3)}{f_1(1 - f_1)}} = 0.8877 \sqrt{\frac{0.4745(1 - 0.4745)}{0.5057(1 - 0.5057)}} = 0.8866$$

$$m_{3,1} = \rho_{3,1} \sqrt{\frac{f_1(1 - f_1)}{f_3(1 - f_3)}} = 0.8877 \sqrt{\frac{0.5057(1 - 0.5057)}{0.4745(1 - 0.4745)}} = 0.8888$$

$$m_{3,8} = \rho_{3,8} \sqrt{\frac{f_8(1 - f_8)}{f_3(1 - f_3)}} = 0.8734 \sqrt{\frac{0.5133(1 - 0.5133)}{0.4745(1 - 0.4745)}} = 0.8742$$

$$m_{8,3} = \rho_{8,3} \sqrt{\frac{f_3(1-f_3)}{f_8(1-f_8)}} = 0.8734 \sqrt{\frac{0.4745(1-0.4745)}{0.5133(1-0.5133)}} = 0.8726$$

Therefore, the solution of the linear system in Eq. 85 is given in column 5 of Table 43. We can then calculate the standard errors associated with the causal effects by the method in par. 4.8.1 and their Z scores $\hat{\lambda}_i/SE[\hat{\lambda}_i]$ (columns 6, 8, respectively). These calculations are performed by the Octave script in par. , but I also loaded matrix M and vectors β, SE on Mathematica 5.2 and I calculated the standard errors for the causal effects by the Mathematica script in par. 4.8.9. Variant rs11147812 is the one with both the largest causal effect and the largest associated Z score for causal effects (Table 43). It is also the one with the lowest p value associated with the marginal effect (Table 38). We can also check the largest error that we make by using Eq. 83 instead of Eq. 73 by using the script in par. 4.7.2.1. In our case the largest value of β is $-1.53E-03$ (Table 38), hence we have that the largest OR is 0.9985, so we run the script for $OR_1 \in [0.9985, 1.0015]$ and we get $\varepsilon \leq 2.8167 \cdot 10^{-7}$ (Figure 12).

4.8.5 Second numerical example (phenotype 20002_1482, females)

We now consider the same data of the previous example, but we add also the variants that are selected if we use a relaxed cut-off for significance of $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ (see Table 46). By following the same algorithm indicated in the previous example, we build Table 45, and Table 46. We then employ the scripts in par. 4.8.8, 4.8.9. In this case, there is a considerable discrepancy between the output of Octave and the one of Mathematica. If we use the values for lambda and its standard error given by Mathematica, we can build Table 47, and as you can see, the result is not compatible with the one calculated in the previous example.

4.8.6 Third Numerical Application (phenotype R53, males)

We now consider the phenotype R53 in males. From the summary statistics provided by Neale's lab we find, after some filtering, the variants in Table 48 to be different in patients vs controls (cut-off: $p = 5 \cdot 10^{-7}$). As can be seen in Table 49, there is a good agreement between the results from Octave and Mathematica, so we consider the Z scores from Octave which identify variant rs2663854 as the causal one. Note that the result is not in agreement with the output of SusieR (see below). The haplotypes and their frequencies in the GBR population, used to solve this case, are collected in Table 5.

4.8.7 SusieR

Among the many tools developed for fine mapping from summary statistics (see [Hutchinson A. et al. 2020](#), table 1), we introduce here SusieR, a software that computes the probability for a variant to be one of the causal variants, also called posterior probability of inclusion (PIP). It also divides the variants into credible sets (CS) which include those variants that are in high LD ([Zou, Y. et al. 2022](#)). When more than one credible set is found, each one of them can include one or more causal variants. A way to use the output of SusieR is to search for the variant with the highest PIP, within each CS (see the example below).

SusieR is a library designed for R compiler. See the website for further information: <https://stephenslab.github.io/susieR/index.html>. The fine mapping calculations on summary statistics are performed by the function `fitted_rss` of the library (see the following example and the script in par. 4.8.10).

rsid	beta	SE beta	p value beta	lambda	SE lambda Octave	SE lambda Mathematica	Z score lambda
rs7337312	-1.4029E-03	2.5188E-04	2.5550E-08	1.0832E-04	2.3491E-03	2.3491E-03	4.6112E-02
rs368309529	-1.5144E-03	2.5510E-04	2.9168E-09	-4.8849E-04	3.5779E-03	3.5779E-03	-1.3653E-01
rs564453195	-1.5144E-03	2.5510E-04	2.9168E-09	-4.8849E-04	3.5779E-03	3.5779E-03	-1.3653E-01
rs7997189	-1.3914E-03	2.5231E-04	3.5011E-08	3.5325E-04	2.5009E-03	2.5009E-03	1.4125E-01
rs1536807	-1.4490E-03	2.5249E-04	9.5458E-09	-8.3586E-05	3.0074E-03	3.0074E-03	-2.7793E-02
rs6563846	-1.4555E-03	2.5207E-04	7.7412E-09	1.9679E-04	4.2109E-03	4.2109E-03	4.6734E-02
rs2282023	-1.4571E-03	2.5209E-04	7.4867E-09	1.6307E-04	4.1911E-03	4.1911E-03	3.8909E-02
rs2282026	-1.4561E-03	2.5217E-04	7.7504E-09	1.9879E-04	4.2541E-03	4.2541E-03	4.6729E-02
rs2017696	-1.4921E-03	2.5243E-04	3.4122E-09	-5.0456E-04	3.9176E-03	3.9176E-03	-1.2879E-01
rs7330720	-1.4852E-03	2.5243E-04	4.0228E-09	-3.8067E-04	3.9847E-03	3.9847E-03	-9.5533E-02
rs11147812	-1.5303E-03	2.5375E-04	1.6348E-09	-7.8045E-04	9.8460E-04	9.8460E-04	-7.9266E-01

Table 43. The causal effects (column 5), their standard errors (column 6, 7), and the associated Z scores (last column). The variant with the largest Z score is highlighted.

variant	rsid	beta	SE	pval	Alt AF cases	Alt AF controls
13:41353297:G:A	rs7337312	-1.40E-03	2.52E-04	2.56E-08	0.4478	0.5057
13:41358365:CT:C	rs368309529	-1.51E-03	2.55E-04	2.92E-09	0.4139	0.4745
13:41358369:T:C	rs564453195	-1.51E-03	2.55E-04	2.92E-09	0.4139	0.4745
13:41363595:T:C	rs7997189	-1.39E-03	2.52E-04	3.50E-08	0.4464	0.5035
13:41369186:G:T	rs9549287	-1.31E-03	2.57E-04	3.42E-07	0.3519	0.4033
13:41369340:C:T	rs9549288	-1.30E-03	2.56E-04	4.04E-07	0.3524	0.4034
13:41369658:C:T	rs1536805	-1.31E-03	2.57E-04	3.15E-07	0.3518	0.4034
13:41369731:A:C	rs1536806	-1.30E-03	2.56E-04	4.01E-07	0.3523	0.4034
13:41369790:A:G	rs1536807	-1.45E-03	2.52E-04	9.55E-09	0.4499	0.5092
13:41370996:A:G	rs6563846	-1.46E-03	2.52E-04	7.74E-09	0.4538	0.5135
13:41371788:A:G	rs2297012	-1.30E-03	2.57E-04	3.98E-07	0.3523	0.4034
13:41372100:T:C	rs9603791	-1.30E-03	2.57E-04	3.96E-07	0.3523	0.4035
13:41372944:C:T	rs2297013	-1.30E-03	2.57E-04	3.92E-07	0.3523	0.4034
13:41374186:T:C	rs2282022	-1.30E-03	2.55E-04	3.43E-07	0.3640	0.4156
13:41374328:C:G	rs2282023	-1.46E-03	2.52E-04	7.49E-09	0.4538	0.5136
13:41374834:G:A	rs2282024	-1.30E-03	2.57E-04	4.04E-07	0.3523	0.4034
13:41376142:A:G	rs9549290	-1.30E-03	2.55E-04	3.30E-07	0.3640	0.4157
13:41376734:C:T	rs9549291	-1.33E-03	2.57E-04	2.41E-07	0.3510	0.4030
13:41376750:C:T	rs34320051	-1.32E-03	2.57E-04	3.11E-07	0.3508	0.4023
13:41377874:C:T	rs9549292	-1.30E-03	2.55E-04	3.35E-07	0.3640	0.4157
13:41380453:A:G	rs3783163	-1.31E-03	2.57E-04	3.51E-07	0.3522	0.4036
13:41381077:G:A	rs2282026	-1.46E-03	2.52E-04	7.75E-09	0.4536	0.5133
13:41382807:T:C	rs60754171	-1.31E-03	2.57E-04	3.37E-07	0.3526	0.4040
13:41383515:A:G	rs2004000	-1.33E-03	2.55E-04	2.11E-07	0.3654	0.4180
13:41384156:A:G	rs9549293	-1.32E-03	2.57E-04	2.45E-07	0.3530	0.4050
13:41384318:A:G	rs7322603	-1.32E-03	2.57E-04	2.58E-07	0.3531	0.4050
13:41384382:C:T	rs7321976	-1.32E-03	2.57E-04	2.94E-07	0.3530	0.4047
13:41387065:T:A	rs2017696	-1.49E-03	2.52E-04	3.41E-09	0.4537	0.5148
13:41390881:G:A	rs7330720	-1.49E-03	2.52E-04	4.02E-09	0.4537	0.5145
13:41404706:T:C	rs11147812	-1.53E-03	2.54E-04	1.63E-09	0.4246	0.4864

Table 44. Statistically significant correlation between phenotype 20002_1482 (females only) and variants at a cut-off for significance of $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$.

RS_Number	Position (hg19)	Ref AF	Alt AF
rs7337312	chr13:41353297	G=0.516,	A=0.483
rs368309529	chr13:41358365	T=0.538,	-=0.462
rs564453195	chr13:41358369	T=0.538,	C=0.462
rs7997189	chr13:41363595	T=0.516,	C=0.483
rs9549287	chr13:41369186	G=0.577,	T=0.423
rs9549288	chr13:41369340	C=0.577,	T=0.423
rs1536805	chr13:41369658	C=0.577,	T=0.423
rs1536806	chr13:41369731	A=0.577,	C=0.423
rs1536807	chr13:41369790	A=0.505,	G=0.494
rs6563846	chr13:41370996	A=0.500,	G=0.500
rs2297012	chr13:41371788	A=0.577,	G=0.423
rs9603791	chr13:41372100	T=0.577,	C=0.423
rs2297013	chr13:41372944	C=0.582,	T=0.418
rs2282022	chr13:41374186	T=0.560,	C=0.440
rs2282023	chr13:41374328	C=0.500,	G=0.500
rs2282024	chr13:41374834	G=0.577,	A=0.423
rs9549290	chr13:41376142	A=0.555,	G=0.445
rs9549291	chr13:41376734	C=0.577,	T=0.423
rs34320051	chr13:41376750	C=0.577,	T=0.423
rs9549292	chr13:41377874	C=0.555,	T=0.445
rs3783163	chr13:41380453	A=0.577,	G=0.423
rs2282026	chr13:41381077	G=0.500,	A=0.500
rs60754171	chr13:41382807	T=0.577,	C=0.423
rs2004000	chr13:41383515	A=0.560,	G=0.440
rs9549293	chr13:41384156	A=0.577,	G=0.423
rs7322603	chr13:41384318	A=0.577,	G=0.423
rs7321976	chr13:41384382	C=0.577,	T=0.423
rs2017696	chr13:41387065	T=0.500,	A=0.500
rs7330720	chr13:41390881	G=0.500,	A=0.500
rs11147812	chr13:41404706	T=0.544,	C=0.456

Table 45. Allele frequencies for the variants in Table 44 form the GBR population.

Haplotype	Count	Frequency
G_T_T_T_G_C_C_A_A_A_A_T_C_T_C_G_A_C_C_C_A_G_T_A_A_A_C_T_G_T	91	0.5
A_-C_C_T_T_T_C_G_G_G_C_T_C_G_A_G_T_T_T_G_A_C_G_G_G_T_A_A_C	70	0.3846
A_-C_C_G_C_C_A_G_G_A_T_C_T_G_G_A_C_C_C_A_A_T_A_A_A_C_A_A_C	5	0.0275
A_-C_C_G_C_C_A_G_G_A_T_C_C_G_G_G_C_C_T_A_A_T_G_A_A_C_A_A_T	4	0.022
G_T_T_T_T_T_T_C_G_G_G_C_T_C_G_A_G_T_T_T_G_A_C_G_G_G_T_A_A_C	3	0.0165
A_T_T_C_G_C_C_A_G_G_A_T_C_T_G_G_A_C_C_C_A_A_T_A_A_A_C_A_A_C	2	0.011
A_T_T_C_G_C_C_A_G_G_A_T_C_T_G_G_A_C_C_C_A_A_T_A_A_A_C_A_A_T	2	0.011
A_-C_C_G_C_C_A_G_G_A_T_C_T_G_G_A_C_C_C_A_A_T_A_A_A_C_A_A_T	1	0.0055
A_-C_C_T_T_T_C_A_G_G_C_T_C_G_A_G_T_T_T_G_A_C_A_G_G_T_A_A_C	1	0.0055
A_-C_C_T_T_T_C_G_G_G_C_C_C_G_A_G_T_T_T_G_A_C_G_G_G_T_A_A_C	1	0.0055
A_-C_C_T_T_T_C_G_G_G_C_T_C_G_A_G_T_T_T_G_A_C_G_G_G_T_A_A_T	1	0.0055
A_-C_C_T_T_T_C_G_G_G_C_T_T_G_A_G_T_T_T_G_A_C_G_G_G_T_A_A_C	1	0.0055

Table 46. Frequencies of all the haplotypes present in GBR population, when we consider the variants collected in Table 44.

rsid	Lambda Mathematica	Lambda Octave	SE lambda Mathematica	Z score lambda
rs7337312	4.89E-05	6.19E-05	0.003016	0.016208
rs368309529	-0.00011	-0.00012	0.004428	-0.02465
rs564453195	-0.00011	-0.00012	0.004428	-0.02465
rs7997189	0.000255	0.000271	0.003279	0.077836
rs9549287	0.389402	-0.05781	25.68178	0.015163
rs9549288	10.07661	0.066095	12937.27	0.000779
rs1536805	-1.08075	-0.04593	43.1065	-0.02507
rs1536806	-9.31568	0.066127	13097.29	-0.00071
rs1536807	-0.00113	-0.00129	0.024969	-0.04508
rs6563846	0.000517	0.000545	0.006052	0.085448
rs2297012	-0.62176	0.065627	385.8671	-0.00161
rs9603791	0.077358	0.057842	73.62608	0.001051
rs2297013	-0.14205	0.025139	27.27955	-0.00521
rs2282022	0.154958	-0.01368	27.3847	0.005659
rs2282023	0.000483	0.000511	0.00602	0.080271
rs2282024	0.854711	0.03051	51.9112	0.016465
rs9549290	-0.05694	0.002	30.85967	-0.00184
rs9549291	-0.16574	-0.16288	3.310716	-0.05006
rs34320051	0.041373	0.043582	1.352009	0.030601
rs9549292	-0.10342	0.00553	48.44616	-0.00213
rs3783163	-0.10216	-0.06443	8.167955	-0.01251
rs2282026	0.00052	0.000548	0.00612	0.084885
rs60754171	0.016602	-0.00564	3.021312	0.005495
rs2004000	0.004785	0.005445	0.102563	0.046656
rs9549293	-0.38228	-0.04326	47.63256	-0.00803
rs7322603	0.307713	-0.03929	45.99443	0.00669
rs7321976	0.045915	0.063753	4.012104	0.011444
rs2017696	-0.00019	-0.00016	0.005584	-0.03345
rs7330720	-6.2E-05	-3.69E-05	0.005689	-0.01095
rs11147812	-0.00018	-0.00025	0.007878	-0.02332

Table 47. The causal effects (column 2, 3), their standard errors (column 4), and the associated Z scores (last column).

variant	rsid	beta	SE	pval	Alt AF cases	Alt AF controls
18:55452281:T:C	rs2571227	9.42E-04	1.81E-04	1.92E-07	0.4301	0.3130
18:55452554:A:G	rs7240802	9.40E-04	1.82E-04	2.27E-07	0.4249	0.3090
18:55452983:A:C	rs2571234	9.39E-04	1.81E-04	2.25E-07	0.4255	0.3095
18:55453784:A:G	rs2850243	9.69E-04	1.82E-04	1.04E-07	0.4219	0.3043
18:55454080:A:G	rs2850244	9.62E-04	1.82E-04	1.32E-07	0.4206	0.3038
18:55454761:G:A	rs62092652	1.08E-03	1.97E-04	4.52E-08	0.3501	0.2422
18:55455694:T:C	rs2663855	1.06E-03	1.96E-04	6.90E-08	0.3536	0.2459
18:55456674:G:A	rs2571236	1.07E-03	1.98E-04	6.02E-08	0.3450	0.2386
18:55458827:C:T	rs2663854	9.47E-04	1.82E-04	1.90E-07	0.4180	0.3026
18:55459217:A:G	rs2663853	9.28E-04	1.81E-04	3.13E-07	0.4171	0.3031
18:55460845:C:T	rs2663851	9.34E-04	1.85E-04	4.57E-07	0.4130	0.3021

Table 48. Statistically significant correlation between phenotype R53 (males only) and variants at a cut-off for significance of $5 \cdot 10^{-7}$. The variant with the lowest p value is highlighted.

rsid	Lambda Octave	Lambda Mathematica	SE Octave	SE Mathematica	Z score Lambda
rs2571227	0.005552	0.005561	0.084312	0.084312	0.065845
rs7240802	-0.0011	-0.00096	0.669382	0.669382	-0.00165
rs2571234	-0.00137	-0.00151	0.668944	0.668944	-0.00205
rs2850243	0.024748	0.024747	0.576504	0.576504	0.042928
rs2850244	0.040852	0.040844	0.845226	0.845226	0.048333
rs62092652	0.005126	0.005128	0.094815	0.094815	0.054062
rs2663855	-0.00249	-0.00249	0.060344	0.060344	-0.04132
rs2571236	-0.00089	-0.00089	0.055462	0.055462	-0.01604
rs2663854	0.063062	0.063069	0.904956	0.904956	0.069686
rs2663853	-0.09315	-0.09314	0.819262	0.819261	-0.1137
rs2663851	-0.03926	-0.03927	0.576075	0.576075	-0.06815

Table 49. The causal effects (column 2, 3), their standard errors (column 4, 5), and the associated Z scores (last column). The variant with the lowest Z score is highlighted.

4.8.7.1 First application

We now run SusieR on the variants collected in Table 43. SusieR will need the array of the beta values, their standard errors, and the matrix of LDs between the variants (the one in Table 41). The script that performs this task is the one in par. 4.8.10. We get as a result a single CS including all the variants but variants 1, 4 (variants are numbered according to the order in Table 41, from the lower position to the higher, on chromosome 14). Within this CS, the variant with the highest PIP is rs11147812 (Figure 13), which is the same variant identified as causal with the method employed in par.4.8.4.

Figure 13. This plot is produced by SusieR (Script in par. 4.8.10) with data in Table 41, Table 43. We see a single CS and its variant with the highest PIP is the last one (rs11147812).

4.8.7.2 Second application

We now run SusieR on the variants collected in Table 44. Variant rs11147812 is the one with the highest PIP within the only CS identified, as in the previous example (Figure 14).

Figure 14. This plot is produced by SusieR (Script in par. 4.8.10) with data in Table 44. We see a single CS and its variant with the highest PIP is the last one (rs11147812).

4.8.7.3 Third application

We now run SusieR on the variants collected in Table 48. Variant rs62092652 is the one with the highest PIP within the only CS identified. It is also the variant with the lowest p value.

Figure 15. This plot is produced by SusieR (Script in par. 4.8.10) with data in Table 48. We see a single CS and its variant with the highest PIP is the last one (rs62092652).

4.8.8 Script, fine-mapping with Octave

```
% file name = fine_mapping
% date of creation = 18/05/2022
clear all
close all
pkg load io % we use package IO for Input/Output
pkg load statistics % we use package statistics
tic % we start counting execution time (seconds)
%-----
% We read details on the xlsx file
%-----
file_name = "20002_1482_filtered_female_fine_mapping.xlsx"
[filetype, sh_names, fformat, nmranges] = xlsfinfo(file_name) % we get info on file_name
```

```

sheet1 = char(sh_names(1,1)) % name of sheet 1
sheet2 = char(sh_names(2,1)) % name of sheet 2
sheet3 = char(sh_names(3,1)) % name of sheet 3
range_1 = substr(char(sh_names(1,2)),5) % number of lines of sheet 1
range_2 = substr(char(sh_names(2,2)),5) % number of lines of sheet 2
range_3 = substr(char(sh_names(3,2)),5) % number of lines of sheet 3
n_v = str2num(range_1)-1; % number of variants
n_h = str2num(range_2)-1; % number of haplotypes
error = 0; % it indicates if some value of d is out of range
%-----
% We read and store the names of the alternative alleles at each position from
% sheet 3 and also their frequencies in the general population
%-----
range = strcat('D2:D',range_3)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread(file_name,sheet3,range);
for i=1:str2num(range_3) - 1
    Alt(i) = substr(char(text(i,1)),1,1);
    Alt_AF_GBR(i) = double(str2num(substr(char(text(i,1)),3)));
endfor
%-----
% We read and store the frequencies of the alternative alleles for the control
% group, from sheet 1, column 21 (U)
%-----
range = strcat('U2:U',range_1)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread(file_name,sheet1,range);
for i=1:n_v
    Alt_AF(i) = double(num(i));
endfor
%-----
% We read the haplotypes and their frequencies from sheet 2 and put them in a
% matrix that has a number of lines given by the number of haplotypes (range_2 - 1)
% and a number of columns equal to the length of the haplotypes
%-----
range = strcat('A2:A',range_2)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread(file_name,sheet2,range);
for i=1:n_h
    h = 1;
    for j=1:2:2*(n_v)-1
        haplo(i,h) = substr(char(text(i,1)),j,1);
        h = h + 1;
    endfor
endfor
range = strcat('B2:B',range_2)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread(file_name,sheet2,range);
for i=1:n_h
    haplo_f(i) = double(num(i));
endfor
den = sum(haplo_f,"double");
haplo_f = haplo_f/den;
%-----
% We read the marginal effects from sheet_1
%-----
range = strcat('N2:N',range_1)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread(file_name,sheet1,range);
beta = double(num);
%-----
% We read the standard errors from sheet_1
%-----

```

```

range = strcat('O2:O',range_1)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread(file_name,sheet1,range);
SE = double(num);
%-----
% We read variants rsid from sheet_1
%-----
range = strcat('D2:D',range_1)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread(file_name,sheet1,range);
rsid = text;
%-----
% We read the p values from sheet_1
%-----
range = strcat('Q2:Q',range_1)
[num,text,row,limits] = xlsread(file_name,sheet1,range);
p_beta = double(num);
%-----
% We calculate the frequencies of the haplotypes of alternative alleles of two loci
%-----
f(1:n_v,1:n_v) = double(0);
for j=1:n_v                                % the position of locus 1
for i=1:n_h                                % the haplotype we are working on
for h=j+1:n_v                              % the position of locus 2
if (haplo(i,j) == Alt(j))
if (haplo(i,h) == Alt(h))
f(j,h) = f(j,h) + haplo_f(i);            % frequency of binary haplotype L_j, L_h
endif
endif
endif
endif
endif
endfor
endfor
endfor
%-----
% We calculate the matrix of the correlation coefficients rho by using allele
% frequencies from the control group in sheet_1
%-----
R(1:n_v,1:n_v) = double(1);
for j=1:n_v - 1
for h=j+1:n_v
D(j,h) = ( f(j,h) - Alt_AF(j)*Alt_AF(h) );
f_a = min(Alt_AF(j), 1-Alt_AF(j));
f_b = min(Alt_AF(h), 1-Alt_AF(h));
if (f_a<f_b)                               % we test the range for d
sup = (1-f_b)*f_a;
inf = -f_a*f_b;
else
sup = (1-f_a)*f_b;
inf = -f_a*f_b;
endif
if (D>sup)
D = sup;
error = error + 1;
elseif (D<inf)
D = inf;
error = error + 1;
endif
R(j,h) = D(j,h)/sqrt( Alt_AF(j)*(1-Alt_AF(j))*Alt_AF(h)*(1-Alt_AF(h)) );
if (R(j,h)>1)                               % we test the range for rho
R(j,h) = 1;
endif
endif
endfor
endfor
endfor

```

```

    if (R(j,h)<-1)
        R(j,h) = -1;
    endif
endfor
endfor
for j=2:n_v
    for h=1:j-1
        R(j,h) = R(h,j);
    endfor
endfor
%-----
% We calculate the final matrix by using allele frequencies from the control
% group in sheet_1
%-----
M(1:n_v,1:n_v) = double(1);
for j=1:n_v - 1
    for h=j+1:n_v
        M(j,h) = R(j,h)*sqrt( (Alt_AF(h)*(1 - Alt_AF(h)))/(Alt_AF(j)*(1 - Alt_AF(j))) );
        if (M(j,h)>1)
            M(j,h) = 1;
        endif
        if (M(j,h)<-1)
            M(j,h) = -1;
        endif
    endfor
endfor
for j=2:n_v
    for h=1:j-1
        M(j,h) = R(j,h)*sqrt( (Alt_AF(h)*(1 - Alt_AF(h)))/(Alt_AF(j)*(1 - Alt_AF(j))) );
        if (M(j,h)>1)
            M(j,h) = 1;
        endif
        if (M(j,h)<-1)
            M(j,h) = -1;
        endif
    endfor
endfor
%-----
% We calculate the causal effects
%-----
A = transpose(M)*M;
B = transpose(M)*beta;
toll = 10^(-9);
maxit = 200;
[lambda, flag, relres, iter, resvec] = pcg(A, B, toll, maxit)
m_lambda = max(abs(lambda))
for i=1:n_v
    if (abs(lambda(i)) == m_lambda)
        true_causal_c = char(rsid(i,1))
        i
    endif
endfor
error = M*lambda - beta % comparison between M*lambda and beta
%-----
% We plot the relative residual as a function of the iterate
%-----
figure(1)
semilogy ([0:iter], resvec / resvec(1), "o-k", "linewidth", 2);

```

```

xlabel ("Iteration",'fontsize',15);
ylabel ("Relative residual",'fontsize',15);
legend ('log(| | M^{T}{\bf{\beta}} - M^{T}M{\bf{\lambda}}| | / | M^{T}{\bf{\beta}}| |)', 'fontsize',15);
grid minor on
%-----
% We calculate the inverse of M
%-----
I(1:n_v,1:n_v) = 0;
for i=1:n_v
    I(i,i) = 1; % we build the identity matrix
endfor
for j=1:n_v
    B = transpose(M)*I(:,j);
    M_inv(:,j) = pcg(A, B, toll, maxit); % column j of the inverse of M
endfor
%-----
% We calculate the matrix for the standard errors of lambda
%-----
M2 = M_inv;
for j=1:n_v
    for h=1:n_v
        M2(j,h) = M2(j,h)^2;
    endfor
endfor
%-----
% We calculate the standard errors for the causal effects
%-----
for i=1:n_v
    SE2(i,1) = SE(i,1)^2;
endfor
SE2_lambda = M2*SE2;
for i=1:n_v
    SE_lambda(i,1) = sqrt(SE2_lambda(i,1));
endfor
%-----
% We calculate the p values for the causal effects
%-----
for i=1:n_v
    p_lambda(i) = double(normcdf(-abs(lambda(i))/SE_lambda(i)));
endfor
%-----
% We write the matrices as .tsv files
%-----
cell_array = cell(n_v,n_v);
for j=1:n_v
    for h=1:n_v
        cell_array(j,h) = f(j,h);
    endfor
endfor
file_name = 'f.tsv'
cell2csv(file_name, cell_array, " ")
%-----
cell_array = cell(n_v,n_v);
for j=1:n_v
    for h=1:n_v
        cell_array(j,h) = R(j,h);
    endfor
endfor

```

```

file_name = 'R.tsv'
cell2csv(file_name, cell_array, " ")
%-----
cell_array = cell(n_v,n_v);
for j=1:n_v
    for h=1:n_v
        cell_array(j,h) = M(j,h);
    endfor
endfor
file_name = 'M.tsv'
cell2csv(file_name, cell_array, " ")
%-----
cell_array = cell(n_v,n_v);
for j=1:n_v
    for h=1:n_v
        cell_array(j,h) = M2(j,h);
    endfor
endfor
file_name = 'M2.tsv'
cell2csv(file_name, cell_array, " ")
%-----
cell_array = cell(n_v,1);
for j=1:n_v
    cell_array(j,1) = beta(j);
endfor
file_name = 'beta.tsv'
cell2csv(file_name, cell_array, " ")
%-----
cell_array = cell(n_v,1);
for j=1:n_v
    cell_array(j,1) = SE(j);
endfor
file_name = 'SE.tsv'
cell2csv(file_name, cell_array, " ")
%-----
% We write the effects, their standard errors, and p values as .tsv files
%-----
cell_array = cell(n_v + 1,7);
cell_array(1,1) = "rsid";
cell_array(1,2) = "beta";
cell_array(1,3) = "SE beta";
cell_array(1,4) = "p value beta";
cell_array(1,5) = "lambda";
cell_array(1,6) = "SE lambda";
cell_array(1,7) = "p value lambda";
for i=1:n_v
    cell_array(i+1,1) = char(rsid(i));
    cell_array(i+1,2) = beta(i);
    cell_array(i+1,3) = SE(i);
    cell_array(i+1,4) = p_beta(i);
    cell_array(i+1,5) = lambda(i);
    cell_array(i+1,6) = SE_lambda(i);
    cell_array(i+1,7) = p_lambda(i);
endfor
file_name = 'results_octave.tsv';
cell2csv(file_name, cell_array, " ")
toc

```

% execution time (seconds)

4.8.9 Script, fine-mapping with Mathematica

This is the Mathematica 5.2 script that performs some of the computations of the previous Octave script (as a check).

```
SetDirectory["C:\Users\macpa\OneDrive\AppData\Local\Microsoft\Windows\OneDrive\Genetics\GWAS\statistics\Fine Mapping"]
M = Import["M.tsv", "Table"]
beta = Import["beta.tsv", "Table"]
SE = Import["SE.tsv", "Table"]
lambda = LinearSolve[M, beta]
Export["lambda_mathematica.tsv", lambda, "Table"]
Minv = Table[Inverse[M]]
Dim = List[Dimensions[M]]
M2 = Minv*Minv
SE2 = SE*SE
SE2lambda = M2 . SE2
SElambda = Table[Sqrt[SE2lambda[[i]]], {i, 1, Dim[[1, 2]]}]
Export["SE_lambda_mathematica.tsv", SELambda, "Table"]\)
```

4.8.10 Script, fine-mapping with R and SusieR

```
# file name = fine_mapping
#
library(susieR)
#
# we read the values beta and SE for each variant
#
fine_map<-read.csv("20002_1482_filtered_female_fine_mapping.csv", sep=";", header = TRUE)
#
# this allows us to refer to the labels of the CSV as variables in the script
#
attach(fine_map)
#
# we calculate the z score
#
z_scores = beta/se
#
# we read the correlation matrix for our variants
#
R<-read.csv("R.tsv", header = FALSE, sep = " ")
#
# we convert R.tsv into a R matrix
#
R2 = data.matrix(R)
#
# we set the max number admitted of causal variants (L) and the sample size (n)
#
n<-190000
L<-10
#
# we use the function fitted_rss of the library susieR to calculate
# the posterior inclusion probability (PIP) of each variant
#
fitted_rss = susie_rss(z_scores, R2, n = n, L = L, z_ld_weight = 0)
#
```

```
# we plot PIP as a function of the variant (numbered from 1 to length(beta))
#
susie_plot(fitted_rss, y="PIP")
#
# we write on the screen a summary of the results
#
summary(fitted_rss)
```